

**The Development of Net Zero Energy Building: The Case for the
Chancellor's Building at Keele University, United Kingdom**

by
Kruti Dineshbhai Bhavsar

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Abstract

Being one of the world's most energy-intensive industries, the building-sector accounts for over 40% of the global energy consumption and is responsible for ~36% of the global-emissions. Keele University, UK under the climate-emergency has pledged to achieve 'carbon-neutrality' by 2030. Reflecting to this, the proposed research-project with a case-study based research-approach, aims to investigate the viability of the transformation of the Chancellor's Building (CB), Keele University into a functional net zero energy building (NZEB) through theoretically retrofitting various green-building technologies (GBTs) & introducing a passive design feature to analyse the clean-energy generation. It also aims to analyse the CB's estimation-based 'annual water-demand profile' by reviewing previous literature. First, the study provides a review of the conceptual development of the field of NZEBs and the state-of-the-art of selected GBTs, that include solar-PV technologies and microgenerating wind-power technologies. Next, with a quantitative methodological approach, the research provides a framework for collecting the required data, such as the CB's present energy-demand & exploratory data analysis (EDA) to analyse the clean-energy generation by retrofitted GBTs & other collected data, in general. Based on the adopted research-methods, the research analysed the CB's annual 'energy demand-supply profile' after theoretically achieving the NZE-status. The results showed that the overall generated clean-energy accounted for 48,740 kWh/year that is more than the CB's annual energy-demand. The study also found that the optimal water-demand profile of the CB is estimated to be 19,170,680.65 litres/year. Overall, the research found that the CB's theoretical transformation into a NZEB is viable. On this basis, it is recommended that the further research is required to analyse the CB's and other large and mixed-use buildings' real-word and practical NZE-transformation. Further research is also needed for analysing more efficient and cutting-edge GBTs in the field of NZEB-development.

Key Words: The Chancellor's Building (CB), Net Zero Energy Building (NZEB), Green Building Technologies (GBTs), Solar-PVs, Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT), Energy Demand Profile, Clean-Energy,

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List of Abbreviations

AC: Alternating Current

ACS: Automated Internal Cleaning Mechanism

ADEPT: Association of Directors of Environment, Economy, Planning and Transport's

a-Si: Amorphous Silicon

BAPV: Building-Applied PVs

BIPV: Building Integrated Photovoltaic

BRE: Building Research Establishment

BREEAM: Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method

CAGR: Compound Annual Growth Rate

CaTiO₃: Calcium Titanium Oxide

CB: The Chancellor's Building

CBA: The Chancellor's Building A

CBB: The Chancellor's Building B

CBC: The Chancellor's Building C

CdTe: Cadmium Telluride

CIS: Copper Indium Selenide

COP: Conference of Parties

CPV: Concentrated PV

c-Si: Crystalline silicon

DC: Direct Current

DDA: Descriptive Data Analysis

EAUC: Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges

EDA: Exploratory Data Analysis

EIA: Environmental Impact Assessment

EU: European Union

GBRT: Green Building Rating Tools

GBTs: Green Building Technologies
Gg: Incident Solar Radiation
GHGs: Greenhouse Gases
GHI: Global Horizontal Irradiation
GWRS: Grey Water Reuse System
HAWTs: Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines
HVAC: Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems
IEQ: Indoor Environmental Quality
IRENA: International Renewable Energy Agency
kg/m³: Kilogram per Cubic Meter (The Unit of Density)
kw: kilowatt (The Unit of Power)
kWh: Kilowatt-hour
LEED: Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
LUC: Land Use Change
MBR: Membrane Bioreactor
MPH: Mile per Hour
NE: North-East
NGBC: National Green Building Council
NGO: Non-Profit Organization
NW: North-West
NZ: Net Zero
NZB: Net Zero Building
NZE: Net Zero Energy
nZEB: Nearly Net Zero Energy Building
NZEB: Net Zero Energy Building
OPEC: Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries
Pa: Pascal (The Unit of Pressure)
POLKA: Pollution Know-how and Abatement
PR: Performance Ratio
PV/T: Photovoltaic Thermal

R&D: Research & Development
R,D&I: Research, Development & Innovation
RET: Renewable Energy Technology
S: South
SE: South-East
SEND: Smart Energy Network Demonstrator
SIMULATE: Smart, Infrastructure and Mobility Urban Laboratory and Test Environment
SLES: Smart Local Energy System
SMBR: Submerged Membrane Bioreactor
SMEs: Medium Enterprises
SNS: Sympathetic Nervous System
Solar PV/T: Photovoltaic Thermal
Solar-PV: Solar Photovoltaic
sq. ft.: Square Foot
SSMI: Scientific Sustainability Metrics & Indices
SW: South-West
TF: Thin-Film
TWh: Terawatt-hours
U.S.D.: U.S. Dollars
UCED: United Nations World Commission on Environment & Development
UNBC: United Nations Brundtland Commission
UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
UNSDGs: United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
USGBC: United States Green Building Council
VGS: Vertical Greenery System
W: Watt (The Unit of Power)
WGBC: World Green Building Council
WW2: World War II
ZE: Zero Energy
ZEB: Zero Energy Building

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The contemporary world is facing some of the great socio-economic and demographic issues, such as continual growth of global-population, urban-rural migration and intensified urbanization process, which have created an array of challenges to environmental quality, resource security, urban planning, international development, sustainable development and so on (Moreno-Monroy et al., 2021). The world's population has increased from 3.36 billion in 1965 to 7.79 billion in 2020 and is estimated to rise continuously to ~9.4 billion by 2050 (**Fig. 1**) (Plecher, 2021). With the increase in global population, the world's overall primary energy-consumption has also climbed from 43,116 TWh in 1965 to 154,620 TWh in 2020 (**Fig. 2**) (Ritchie et al., 2020). Moreover, presently, ~55% of the global-population resides in the world's urban-areas, that is estimated to expand rapidly to ~70% by the year 2050, indicating a growth of ~26% in the global energy-consumption from today's level (Knudsen et al., 2020). Population-growth along with the spatial-expansion of the built-land has triggered the worldwide land use changes (LUC), leading to a remarkable growth in the global compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of building and construction-sector. The CAGR for building and construction-sector accounted for ~6% in 2021 and is expected to rise further to 11.8% by the end of 2022 (Nuissl and Siedentop, 2021) (UNEP, 2021).

Figure 1. Global Population and Global Urban-Population Increase from 1965 to 2020 (Redrawn after Ritchie and Roser, 2020; Roser et al., 2020) (**Note:** See, Appendix [A]-1)

With the overpopulation and overurbanization, the global annual CO₂-emission has also increased from 1.95 billion tonne in 1900 to 34.81 billion tonnes in 2020 (**Fig. 3**), wherein the historical CO₂-emitting sectors like energy-generation, heat and transportation still contribute the most (Ritchie and Roser, 2021). However, being one of the world's most energy-intensive industries, building and construction-industry accounts for ~40% of the global energy consumption & is responsible for about 36% of the world's overall greenhouse gas (GHGs)-emissions. The convergence of the need to mitigate the global climate-change, reduce the

overuse of energy and innovate operational-alternatives to decarbonize building and construction-sector provided a stepping-stone of ‘sustainable architecture’ (Ohene et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Increase in Global Primary Energy Consumption from 1965 to 2020 (Redrawn after Jutta and van Zanden, 2020; Ritchie et al., 2020) (Note: See, Appendix [A]-1)

Figure 3. Increase in Annual CO2 Emissions (Fossil Fuel and Land Use Change) in Billion Tonnes from 1965 to 2020 (Redrawn after Ritchie and Roser, 2020) (Note: See, Appendix [A]-1)

1.2. The Concept of Sustainable Architecture

“Sustainable architecture is defined as the architecture that consciously incorporates ecologically-responsible building & management practices to minimize the harmful environmental-impacts of building through improving the material, space and resource-efficiency while sustaining the ecological elements like natural-light, air-flow, green-spaces within the built-spaces” (Bennetts et al., 2002; Ebersole, 2022). The need to sustain environmental-elements into architecture within the building’s functional-boundaries through the help of design and modern-technologies became the motto of sustainable-architecture.

Simultaneously, ‘green-architecture’, that solely focuses on the environmental-aspects of the building, became the commercial-alternative of the term ‘sustainable-architecture’. “Green architecture is an architectural-approach that minimizes the resource-consumption from the building’s construction-phase to building-operations by incorporating environmental-friendly building-materials & construction-practices” (Ragheb et al., 2016). By reducing negative-impacts of building-waste, emissions, polluting-materials, the green-architectural practices seek to safeguard the environment-surrounding. However, in 1987, when the United Nations Brundtland Commission (UNBC) defined sustainability as “*fulfilling the present generations’ requirements without compromising the needs of the future generations*”, the term ‘sustainable-architecture’ became more distinctive (Guy and Farmer, 2001; Gauzin-Müller and Favet, 2002; The United Nations, No Date). Sustainable architecture incorporates all three pillars of sustainability: ecology, economy and society. Thus, it is an imperative pursuit of today’s world that needs to be enrooted in the current theoretical and practical-frameworks of architecture to drive effective changes (Bennetts et al., 2002).

1.2.1. What Is the Net Zero Energy Building (NZEB)?

In the late 20th-century, the debate of climate change became visible in building-sector due to the ever-increasing greenhouse gas (GHG)-emissions and high energy-consumption, associated with the building’s construction, operations and activities. This phenomenon introduced the next-generation concept of green-buildings, which incorporated renewable-energy technologies to achieve the ‘net zero-status’. These ‘net zero buildings (NZBs)’ or ‘net zero energy buildings (NZEBs)’ emerged as a potential solution for the future of the building-industry that integrated modern green building technologies (GBTs), passive design-features & smart-devices. In simpler terms, NZEBs are energy-efficient, cost-efficient and environmentally-sustainable building solutions to curtail the buildings’ dependency on the primary-energy, main-grid, hence, the conventional-resources (**Fig. 16**) (Deng et al., 2014, Darko et al., 2017).

There is a lack of uniformity in the international-definition of the NZEBs due to its self-explanatory nature. This is because the NZEBs-designs (**Fig. 17**) differ depending on the building-type, available energy-infrastructure, location of the building & climate-type. Additionally, the NZEBs’ definitions do not require a distinctive and deeper understanding of energy-consumption & management. Hence, researchers’ approaches towards the NZEB-definitions vary depending on the buildings’ type, requirements and national policy-standards of the NZEB-frameworks. However, the NZEB, at its core, strives to minimize the building’s energy-consumption while maximizing the on or/and off-site clean energy-production (Marszal et al., 2012; Wells, et al., 2018; Lin and Chen, 2022). Thus, with an inclusive approach, the NZEBs can be defined as, “the energy-efficient buildings that generate clean-

energy that is equal to or more than the buildings' energy-use". The on or/and off-site renewable-energy generating resources include solar photovoltaic (Solar-PV), geothermal heating-systems, wind-turbines, biomass storage-systems and/or passive architectural features like energy-efficient windows, green-walls, high-performance insulated-walls, high-efficiency appliances (e.g., water and air-filtration devices & heating ventilation and air conditioning systems or HVAC) (Sartori et al., 2012; Feng et al., 2019; Shirinbakhsh and Harvey, 2021).

1.2.2. The Need for Improving the Energy-Efficiency of the Buildings

Before proposing the major aims and objectives of this research, it is crucial to address the following questions: Why is the buildings' energy profile important & why is there a need to improve the buildings' energy-efficiency?

As mentioned earlier, the building-sector is responsible for ~40% and 36% of the world's overall energy-consumption and GHG-emissions, respectively. In the countries like U.S.A. and China, the building-industry consumes ~40% of the total primary-energy, generated and the data is somewhat similar for majority of the countries across the globe (Liu at al., 2022; Ritchie and Roser, 2020). As a basic-component, energy plays a vital role in building-operations, maintenance and sustenance of building-performance throughout its lifespan. Enhancing the buildings' overall energy-outlook in commercial, residential and industrial-sectors is crucial in order to improve the human well-being, work efficiency and productivity. Thus, the buildings' energy-profile is important while addressing the building-performance. The improvements in building-performance can only be achieved by structural-changes like improving the basic form and architecture, system-components (i.e., electrical and/or mechanical devices) & energy-efficiency of the buildings (Danish et al., 2019; Liu at al., 2022). "Energy-efficient buildings refer to the structures, having minimal energy-consumption & maximum resource-efficiency". More clearly, they are the buildings with enhanced resource-efficiency that provide the same building-services with less energy-costs. Moreover, energy has a reciprocal-relationship with the global-economy and is the primary-component of its foundation. Therefore, curbing the energy-consumption can significantly reduce the global-finances, required for energy-production, distribution and other operational-costs. This improves the productivity of economic-sectors while lowering the global-emissions, promoting the sustainable growth and establishing energy-security in the energy-deficient areas. This indicates a clear need for the expansion of the energy-efficient infrastructure, wherein the concepts like NZEBs can contribute remarkably. This is because it directs the building-sector towards renewables and novel energy-saving interventions (Ionescu et al., 2015).

1.3.The Research Problem

The proposed research-project aims to investigate the viability of the transformation of the Chancellor's building (CB) at Keele University into a functional-NZEB through theoretically or conceptually retrofitting various GBTs and introducing a passive design feature to generate clean-energy, that equals to the CB's annual energy-demand profile. Next, the research aims to analyse the estimation-based annual water-demand profile of the CB through reviewing literature. Here, the GBTs will include the renewable-energy technologies like rooftop/terrace mounted solar-PVs, Solar PV trees, small-scale vertical wind-turbines & a passive-feature of green-facades (**Table 12**). Overall, this research chiefly focuses on the CB's theoretical or conceptual transformation into a NZEB to analyse 'the clean-energy generation' & CB's 'energy demand-&-supply profile'. The concept of the CB's conceptual-conversion to a NZEB

& reduce its dependency on the main electrical-grid aligns with Keele University’s sustainability-target of 2030 to achieve ‘carbon-neutrality’.

1.3.1. Significance of the Proposed-Research Project

Nearly 55% of the world’s total electricity is consumed by buildings for various building-operations, thus the global interest in NZEB-market is constantly increasing. The global NZEB-market accounted for \$18.37 billion in 2020 and is expected to grow to \$47.7 billion by 2026 (Koons, 2022). However, currently only <1% of the buildings have achieved the NZE-status (Laski and Burrows, 2022), globally. This indicates a clear need for the expansion of the ‘net zero infrastructure-development’. Moreover, a majority of the studies, conducted in the last three-decades in this field largely focus on enhancing energy and cost-efficiency of the buildings, located in the urban and semi-urban settings (Omrany et al., 2022). This indicates a clear existing-gap in the research, development (R&D) and expansion of the NZEBs in non-urban areas. Thus, investigations into the case-studies, based in non-urban settings are significant to catalyse the research, development & innovations (R,D&I) for identifying the opportunities, demands and limitations of NZEB-development (Feng et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2022). The R&D for the expansion of the rural-NZEBs can potentially bring various academic-institutions, researchers and industrial stakeholders together from local, national and international-levels, providing a platform to advance the field. Keele’s strategic plan states that “*the university aims to promote environmental sustainability in all that we do*” (Emes, W., 2021). Keele represents a rural university-campus with high sustainability-standards. Besides, being a mixed-use building, the CB has a large energy-demand profile. Hence, the case-study of the CB at Keele will provide an example for theoretically developing a university based-NZEB, located in the rural-setting with temperate maritime climate-zone, making the first case of its kind at Keele. This research has potential scopes of its real-world development in the future, which can constructively affect Keele’s sustainability-credentials & overall energy-outlook.

1.4. Background of the Location: Keele University, United Kingdom

Figure 4. The Location of Keele University in the UK, Image Coordinates: Latitude 54°37’20.80” N and Longitude 2°12’48.25” W (Google Earth, No Date. a)

Keele University is one of the UK's largest integrated-campus public universities with over 600-acre estate, located in a green-setting of Staffordshire, the Midlands of West-Central England (**Fig. 4, 5**). The university-campus is home to ~1500 species of flora and fauna (Keele University, No Date. I; Keele University, No Date. k) and houses 323 buildings (Data Received from Keele Estate-team; Keele University, No Date. b) (**Fig. 6**).

Figure 5. Location of Keele University in the Midlands of West-Central England, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00'13.76" N and Longitude 2°13'41.38" W (Google Earth, No Date. b)

Figure 6. The Campus of Keele University, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00'20.16" N and Longitude 2°16'45.25" W (Google Earth, No Date. c) (**Note:** For the digital campus-map, see Appendix [C]-1)

1.4.1. Keele University Energy Management Strategy (EMS)

The Keele EMS was a strategic-framework (2013-2015) to manage energy within the campus through reducing university's dependency on gas and main-grid electricity to curb university's overall emissions. Keele has a target to achieve 28% energy-efficiency by the year 2022 against the baseline of 2015-2016. Thus, the university embodied an updated version of EMS, called 'Environment & Energy Policy' (i.e., a 2016-2022 framework) in 2016, that aimed to increase university's clean energy-generation, energy-capacity, energy-efficiency and manage costs while decreasing environmental impacts (Jones and Evans, 2016). This framework fostered sustainability at Keele by a range of investments in various sustainability and energy-efficiency projects, some of which are ongoing or still under development (**Table 1**) (Keele University, No Date. m). The EMS significantly improved university's metering-capacity by deploying a metering-system throughout the campus, that deliver accurate measurements of university's energy-consumption. As a part of EMS, Keele implemented a 'sustainability-framework' that measures and supervises the university's activities related to sustainability and its environmental-credentials (Jones and Evans, 2016).

1.4.2. Sustainability at Keele

Leading in sustainability, Keele University can become an ideal home for the R,D&I in the NZE infrastructure development, aligning with a number of national, international climate-goals and sustainable development-targets. Keele declared a 'climate-emergency' in 2019, reflecting which it pledged to achieve 'carbon-neutrality' by 2030 under the net zero target initiative in the education-sector, led by Environmental Association for Universities and Colleges (EAUC) with the support from the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (Keele University, No Date. m). This pledge mirrors the UK Government's 'sustainable development ambitions', aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs), 2015 & 'GHG-emissions reduction obligations' under the COP26 climate summit, 2021. These have provided Keele a target to curb its emissions to 33-34% by 2020 (i.e., achieved) & 80% by 2050 (i.e., proceeding) against the 1990-baseline, through incorporating various R&D-projects to improve university's green-credentials & make the campus more sustainable (Emes, W., 2021; Keele University, No Date. a). Keele has a number of academic-courses, surrounding the environment and sustainability along with numerous, cutting-edge R,D&I-projects (Keele University, No Date. m) as mentioned in (**Table 1**).

Currently, as a part of 'Low Carbon Project', Keele has become a home for the European first 'Smart Energy Network Demonstrator (SEND)-programme'. SEND has provided Keele a unique platform for on-campus clean energy-production by developing a low-carbon energy generation park. With multiple renewables, it generates, distributes & stores energy to make Keele-campus energy-independent. SEND-programme created a framework for saving ~4100 tonnes of CO₂-equivalents a year by 2021 (**Table 2**) (Keele University, No Date. c; f).

Table 1(continued). The List of Major Past and Present R&D Projects at Keele University, UK, Leading Towards Sustainability for Keele’s Carbon-Neutral Future.

No.	Project Name	Major Aim	Remark
1.	HyDeploy <i>Source:</i> (Keele University, No Date. j)	-To encourage the low-carbon ‘Hydrogen-led economy’ via ground-breaking experimental trial, combining hydrogen with the campus’s natural gas network to heat homes and buildings	Keele campus, under the HyDeploy-project, performed the trial (2019-2021) of injection of up to 20% (i.e., by volume) of hydrogen into Keele’s pre-existing natural gas network, which is highest in Europe along with the Engie project of Northern-France.
2.	Pollution Know-how and Abatement (POLKA) <i>Source:</i> (Keele University, No Date. d)	-To innovate a technological solution for the replacement of engine-combustion of fossil fuels. -To innovate the hydrogen-based combustion systems like aero-engines, gas-turbines and boilers, as renewable-alternatives of CO ₂ along with finding potential solutions for challenges in the process of combusting. -To encourage ‘zero emission fuels’ on international level through research & innovation.	A 2020 European Funding Programme for Research and Innovation, ‘Horizon’ awarded Keele professor Maria Heckl a funding to foster renewable energy through technological innovations. The programme will include a range of academic institutions and partner companies.
3.	Rugeley <i>Source:</i> (Keele University, No Date. e)	-To develop a novel ‘zero-carbon energy system’ for the residents of the town of Rugeley, Staffordshire to save energy, deliver cleaner as well as cheaper energy and reduce the carbon emissions. -To engage local community with sustainability and create jobs, locally	Keele along with the ENGIE created scalable and efficient energy solutions (i.e., Smart Local Energy System or SLES) for this town through proposing mixed-use development and running various projects related to clean energy management. The project ran under the Engie, as a part of consortium until 2021, including a number of acting members from various places, working on an array of energy projects.
4.	Smart, Infrastructure and Mobility Urban Laboratory and Test Environment (SIMULATE) <i>Source:</i> (Keele University, No Date. g)	-To design, demonstrate, manage and test the smart highway networks to extend it to the local roads through adapting new and locally-suitable, yet strategic road networks. -To address and combat the challenges in the path to achieve sustainable mobility & air-quality at local scale.	Keele, as a ‘living laboratory’ under the joint bid to the Association of Directors of Environment, Economy, Planning and Transport’s (ADEPT) has a leading vision to find effective radical solutions for issues of air quality by connecting local businesses, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Staffordshire. Keele as an academic leader, provided this programme not only the cutting-edge research but also an on-campus centre, ‘the Innovation Hub’. The project is

			funded by the Department for Transportation.
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Table 2. Framework of the SEND-Project at Keele University with Major Project Ambitions and Outcomes (Keele University, No Date. f; Robinson and Briggs, 2018)

	Fostering sustainability through smart and renewable energy generation, improving Keele’s sustainability profile.
	An on-campus ‘low carbon energy generation park’ as an international test-bed, known as Keele’s ‘living-laboratory’ with over 12,000, 150kW solar-PVs and two Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) to produce renewable energy (Figure 7). The solar-farm and the wind turbines (-both combined) consist the capacity of 5.5 MW and 1.8 MW, respectively along with a 1MW of battery storage system.
	Presently generating around 50% of the campus-electricity by cutting around 1500 tonnes of CO ₂ e per annum.
	Energy storage, distribution and balancing for establishing unique systems for energy generation, utilization & management.
	Reduce the university’s reliance on conventional resources like fossil-fuels and curb the overall campus emissions.
	International R & D, partnership opportunities for university staff, students, research academics, other academic institutions and global stakeholders.
	To carry out novel research and business for ‘economic-growth’, by creating jobs at local and/or national level, i.e. termed as ‘clean-growth’.

Figure 7. The Low Carbon Energy Generation Park with over 12,000 Solar-PVs and 2 Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs), Keele University (Keele University, No Date. c)

1.4.3. Significance of the Location

Implementing specifications with respect to building-design, its components, use of materials and exploitation of clean sustainable-resources for electricity-generation are the most crucial steps to enhance the energy-efficiency and reduce emissions. Thus, the research with a scope of future advancements towards the ‘net-zero’ in academia is imperative in order to lay the foundation of the real-world solutions (Wilberforce et al., 2021). Keele as an active research-university is successfully expanding its vision towards sustainability and has a great potential for embodying novel research-projects and innovative future-developments due to the design of its on-campus infrastructure, that can lead Keele to its carbon-neutrality target. This indicates a symbiotic relationship between Keele University (i.e., the location) of this proposed research-project and the analysis of the viability of the CB’s conceptual transformation to a NZEB (i.e., the proposed-research).

1.4.4. The Case-Study Location: The Chancellor’s Building, Keele University

The Chancellor’s building (CB) is a 3-story building, integrating 3 different buildings: A (CBA), B (CBB) and C (CBC) (**Fig. 8, 9**). Next, the main central building-CBA is divided into three zones: (i) Zone 1-The Foyer, (ii) Zone 2-The Gallery & (iii) Zone 3-The Exhibition Suite, next to the Westminster Theatre (Keele University, No Date. b; h). North to the Hornbeam-building, the CB is an ideal model-building for this case-study-based research, because it is one of the largest, mixed-use buildings at Keele University, directly facing slight-South East. It houses a total of 419 utility-spaces (i.e., including all 3-floors) and a total ground area-cover of 8,786 m² with high energy-use profile with a number of offices, café & catering-spaces, teaching, administration and research-spaces (see Appendix [A]-10) (Keele University, 2022). Conversion of this large, multi-purpose and high energy-consuming building to a NZEB can significantly affect Keele’s overall energy-outlook, reduce emissions and help Keele achieve its carbon-neutrality target within the set timeframe.

Figure 8. The Chancellor’s Building (CB), Featuring the All Three Zones, CBA in the Middle, CBB at Down Left Corner in the Front & CBC at the Top Right Corner, Keele University, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00’14.42” N and Longitude 2°16’27.52” W (Redrawn After Google Earth, No Date. d) (**Note:** For the multi-directional views of the CB, see Appendix [C]-2 to 4; For digital floor-maps, see Appendix [C]-5 to 7; For the room facilities map, see Appendix [C]-9)

Figure 9. The Chancellor's Building (CB), Featuring the All Three Zones, CBA, CBB & CBC, Keele University (Primary Visual Data Collected and Created by the Author)

Figure 10. Main Entrance of the Chancellor's Building, Featuring Various Internal-Spaces of the Chancellor's Building: A Mixed-Used Building Including the Westminster Theatre, Audio-Visual Service Space, Food-Court and Café, Learning Spaces & Academic Departments and Schools (Primary Visual Data Collected and Edited by the Author)

1.5. Major Research Scopes & Limitations

The proposed 'case-study' based-research formulates a framework for the theoretical transformation of the CB's into to a NZEB and make it energy-independent. The research-boundaries will extend to the set milestones (Appendix [A]-2), that will be achieved at the completion of each stage of the proposed-research. By comparing and analysing the CB's 'present annual energy-profile' & 'yearly clean-energy generation' by the retrofitted GBTs after its conceptual-transformation into a NZEB, this research will calculate the CB's energy demand-supply profile. This will be used to establish overall conclusion of the CB's capacity/practicality to achieve a NZE-status and contribute to Keele's pledge of reaching carbon-neutrality in the future. The carbon-neutrality programme at Keele will require interlinked and extended solutions, real-world projects like the proposed case-study model that have the future scopes for university-based development.

However, there are some factors, limiting the research-boundaries. This master's-level dissertation-research project is restricted to theoretical-transformation of the model-building and does not involve its field-testing or development at this stage. As explained earlier, the shorter time-period, involved cost or mammoth-sized project-budget and large amount of manpower are three major limiting-factors due to which, the research boundaries cannot stretch beyond the analysis of the CB's theoretical transform into a NZEB. Incorporating Keele's other large, mixed-use buildings in the proposed-research would make remarkably impactful findings. However, to conduct a multi-model study in the allotted research-period seems overambitious and therefore, impractical. Next, the generalization of the research-framework for other buildings' NZE-transformation is challenging because of the subjectivity of the presented case-study and distinctive building-typology. Although, the project has potential scopes of future development, it's real-world development may cause disturbance to the academic & non-academic activities, running in the CB. The detailed research-limitations and future prospects of development will be discussed further in the proposed-research.

1.6 Research Aims and Objectives

Aim: The proposed research-project aims to “investigate the viability of the transformation of the Chancellor's building (CB) at Keele University into a functional net zero energy building (NZEB) through theoretically or conceptually retrofitting various green-building technologies (GBTs) and a passive design feature to generate clean-energy, that equals to the CB's annual energy-demand profile”. The research also aims to “analyse the estimation-based annual water-demand profile of the CB through reviewing literature”.

For the total fulfilment of the proposed research-aims, following objectives will be attained.

O.1 To collect primary and secondary data through using a range of data-collection methods, mentioned in (Table 13) to analyse the viability of the GBT-retrofits and the selected passive design feature (Table 12) for the proposed research-project.

O.2 To conduct a literature review for analysing an internationally-inclusive, concept-based emergence & evolution of the field of NZEBs in a chronological-order as well as the state-of-the-art of the selected-GBTs (Table 12) for the proposed research-project.

O.3 To calculate the overall 'clean-energy', generated by the retrofitted-GBTs through using the collected-data & analyse the yearly 'energy demand-supply profile' of the CB after

achieving net-zero criteria as well as to review literature for estimating annual ‘water demand-profile’ of the CB to ultimately synthesize the chief findings of this research-project.

O.4 To discuss the possible post-development impacts of the ‘NZE-Chancellor’s building’ on Keele community and university’s overall energy-outlook through critically analysing the obtained findings & reviewing the previous literature as well as make future research-recommendations.

Next, the research will conduct the review of previous literature, incorporate research-methodology for creating a framework to analyse the collected data & establish findings.

2. Review of Literature

Majority of the studies in the field of green and NZE-buildings have explored the areas like ‘building-materials’, ‘energy-efficient designs’ & ‘environmental-impacts of the green-buildings’. However, there is a visible-gap in an internationally-inclusive and clear understanding of the thematic-development of the concepts of green & NZE-buildings (Omrany et al., 2022; Mazzeo, Liu and Chen, 2022; D. and Oliveti, 2020; Wells et al., 2018). First, with a ‘conceptual review-approach’, this literature-review provides a chronological and concept-based ‘emergence & evolution of the green and NZE-buildings’ & specifies the terms’ understanding. Second, it provides a glimpse into the ‘state-of-the-art’ of the selected GBTs for the proposed case-study.

2.1. From Sustainable to Green Architecture: Emergence & Evolution

A Swizz-French modern architect, Le Corbusier once famously quoted that “*Architecture is the starting point for anyone who wants to take humanity towards a better future*” (Corbusier, 2013).

Architecture is ‘*the art and science of building*’. Expanding the term’s understanding more clearly, architecture in practice, can be defined as “the art, combined with science and techniques to plan, design and build, as distinguished from the skills, associated with construction”. It envelops the knowledge of various fields, such as history, craft, design, mathematics, geometry, engineering & cultural, aesthetic and environmental studies (Roth and Clark, 2019; Parcell, 2012). Definitions of architecture vary depending on the perspectives and ideological-basis but the practice, at its core, entails the building’s utilitarian, functional and aesthetic aspects (Colquhoun, 2002).

In the early-19th century, architecture started shifting towards the modern-age, bringing the radical and reformist ideas of ‘avant-garde’ tendencies (Colquhoun, 2002). By the mid-19th century, these changes represented a transformation against inherited-eclecticism in the arts alongside the growing industrialization and capitalization in the West, reflecting the concerns of environmental-degradation. Degrading country-areas and resource-pollution like land, air and water across Europe and U.S.A. gave birth to the biocentrism, that started influencing the inherited Western-anthropocentric traditions (McCormick, 1991; Kopnina et al., 2018). Subsequently, the late-19th century gave birth to the ‘contemporary environmental-movement’ led architects to address the climate-issues (Colquhoun, 2002, Conway and Roenisch, 2005) in their work.

In the first half of 20th century, the post-World War II (WW2)-architect, Le Corbusier radicalized the inherited baroque and victorian architectures by replacing it with the modern-forms. He simplified structures by implying ‘reductive-functionalism’ (**Fig. 11**), a philosophy of architecture that signifies the practical considerations of the buildings, such as its functions, utility. Corbusier’s passive design-approaches like ‘open, clean geometric-forms’, ‘systematic utilization and visual-purification of spaces’ through minimalist-design along with the ‘efficient use of natural-elements’ promoted sustainability in architecture (Gans and Corbusier, 2006; Corbusier, 2013). Subsequently, the 20th century architects incorporated ‘sustainability’ in their works to preserve environment within the built-space and improve human well-being. Finally, in the 1970s, the distinctive concept of ‘sustainable-architecture’ was introduced, that established the relationship between nature and people within the built-spaces (Bennetts et al.,

2002). Louise Kahn, an American modern-architect incorporated traditional-materials and red-bricks while using symmetry to provide focus to the structures (**Fig. 12**). Kahn’s modern-designs perpetuated ‘natural-elements’ like natural-light and air-flow & ‘quintessential building-materials’ (Lobell and Kahn, 2008; The School of Life, 2022). The modern architects relied on science, engineering and technologies to fulfil the needs of modern-humans (Martek et al., 2018).

The contemporary-environmentalism emerged, initially from the arising concerns of human-health that were the products of ‘industrial-revolution’ (Kline, 2022). This phenomenon shifted the purpose of the buildings as cultural-assets to economic/capitalistic-assets (Ragheb et al., 2016). The long-standing destructiveness of the WW2, environmental-degradation through the high-industrial age as well as the 1970s-energy-crisis (i.e. the OPEC or OAPEC- Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries oil crisis of 1972 & the second oil crisis of 1973) of the West led the world to oil-scarcity, high fuel-prices. This energy-crisis accompanied by the omnivorous-globalization and swiftly expanding suburban-sprawl of the late-20th century, demanded constructive-changes in the urban-living styles (Onion et al., 2010; Wines, 2019). These reasons led experts to redefine the architecture of the times, which established the concept of ‘green-architecture’.

Figure 11. The Most Important Modern Architectural Works by Le Corbusier, Featuring Passive Designs and Efficient Use of Space (Carter, 2016)

Figure 12. The Building of Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad (IIMA), India, Designed by Louis Kahn (Notable Aspects: Building’s Scale, Traditional Building-Materials & Use of Light & Space”) (Redrawn after Ravenscroft, T., 2021)

2.1.1. Green-Architecture

The need to restore the global-economy from the hit of 1970s-energy-crisis and balance the global energy-demand laid the slab of sustainable development. The Brundtland Report, 1987 by the United Nations World Commission on Environment & Development (UCED) signified the alignment of socio-economic growth with the natural-world and its preservation (Kibert, 2016). Following to which, the principles of sustainable development were declared in 1992 at the Rio, UCED. Later, in 2002 the Johannesburg World Summit on Sustainable Development conceptualized the ‘sustainable-consumption & production’ for resource-efficiency, development of clean-technologies to promote ‘sustainable economic growth’ (Von Frantzius, 2004; The United Nations, No Date). Previous studies have compared and defined green-architecture as sustainable-architecture, because both find their roots in the principles of sustainable-development and emphasize wholistic-sustainability of the three ‘P’s (i.e., preservation, people, profit)’ (Ragheb et al., 2016; Conte, 2018). However, green-architecture is a ‘conceptual-advancement’ of sustainable-architecture and not a similar concept and/or term as green-architecture incorporates many advanced-features that are not necessarily present in the sustainable-structures.

Green-architecture incorporates operational-features (i.e., GBTs), practical-aspects (i.e., recycling-practices), passive design features (i.e., natural, eco-friendly materials) into the indoors and outdoors of the buildings to create a healthy and energy-efficient built-environment (Gauzin-Müller and Favet, 2002). The U.S. Office of the Federal Environmental Executive in the 1990s separated the concept of green and sustainable-architecture by stating that “the green-buildings are energy, water, material and cost-efficient structures with minimized waste and carbon-footprint & maximized use of renewable-energy” (OFEE, 2006; Ragheb et al., 2016). In this sense, every green-architecture is ‘sustainable’ in nature but every sustainable-architecture is necessarily ‘green’. Green-buildings focus on the buildings’ present sustainability-level of the 3-‘P’s, whereas the sustainable-buildings signify the long-term

sustainability-goals. A net zero energy (NZE)-structure is a very good example of green-architecture as it addresses overall performance-efficiency (i.e., resource, material & design-efficiency). A NZE-building is an advanced green-building that has a balanced energy demand-supply profile (Fig. 16).

2.1.2. Green Building Rating Tools or Systems (GBRTs/GBRSs)

The heightened energy-demand and carbon-emissions in the building-industry led construction-authorities in the 1990s to established green-benchmarking standards for the ‘green-construction’. GBRT, as a tool to evaluate, elevate sustainability achievements of the buildings, measures the structure’s socio-ecological impacts. It uses a set of standardized performance-threshold, that the green-building should meet. There are ~600 national GBRTs, world-wide, based on various target-values and sustainability-categories (Shan and Hwang, 2018) for building-rating. The two-chief GBRTs, listed below are the ‘third-party assessment tools’ with certain credit-points. They provide certifications to the green-structures for the pre-decided sustainability-categories (Awadh, 2017).

- **BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method)**

First published as the Building Research Establishment (BRE), England, 1990, BREEAM is a globally-validated GBRT for analysing, rating & certifying the sustainable-achievement of the buildings (BREEAM, No Date). Assessed by the independent standard-licensed assessors, the buildings’ environmental-performance is measured through an ‘*in-use global environmental assessment method*’, that includes 2 processes: (i) an overall performance-assessment from construction to renovation & (ii) building-management for the buildings’ operational, management-efficiency (Lee and Burnett, 2008). BREEAM-assessment covers environmental-categories as mentioned in (Table 3). With a BREEAM-community in over 87 nations, it has certified ~560,000 buildings with ~2 million new under registry for certification, globally (BREEAM, No Date).

Table 3. A Table, Showing BREEAM Rating, Related Environmental Categories & Levels (BREEAM, No Date)

BREEAM Certification Score	Rating-Levels with Star Marking (i.e., for all types of building-projects)
<30	Unclassified: 0 Star
≥30	Pass: 1 Star
≥45	Good: 2 Stars
≥55	Very Good: 3 Stars
≥70	Excellent: 4 Stars
≥85	Outstanding: 5 Stars

- **LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design)**

The United States Green Building Council (USGBC) was founded to promote environmentally-responsible and cost-efficient greener-construction through integrating various sub-industries of the building-sector. The USGBC in 1993 created a green building certification program, called LEED for analysing the green-building’s design, construction, operation and the overall-performance (USGBC, 2022). LEED-certification has ‘4 credit-based levels, starting from credit 40 to 80 +’ (Table 4) for ‘7 different categories’ (Table 5) (Lee and Burnett, 2008) for the buildings’ sustainability-achievement. It is structured to align with the

UNSDGs by saving energy with lowering operation-costs and carbon-footprint. LEED has become a global green-rating tool with more than 100,000 LEED-certified projects in ~167 nations to date (Benjamin, 2017).

Table 4. Different Levels of LEED Certification with Points (ESCSI, 2022; RTS, No Date)

LEED Certification-Levels	Points/Credits
LEED® Certified	40 – 49
Silver	50 – 59
Gold	60 – 79
Platinum	80 +

Table 5. Different Categories for LEED Certification with the Building-Type (ESCSI, 2022; RTS, No Date)

No.	Categories of the Buildings’ Sustainable-Achievements	Total Possible Points for Specific Category: for Existing Building	Total Possible Points for Specific Category: for Homes	Total Possible Points for Specific Category: for Commercial Interiors
1.	Sustainable Site	26	22	21
2.	Water Efficiency	10	15	11
3.	Innovation in Design	6	11	6
4.	Energy & Atmosphere	35	38	37
5.	Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	15	21	17
6.	Regional Priority	4	(Note: This category for homes relates to ‘Location & Linkages’) 10	4
7.	Materials Used & Resources	14	16	14
Total Points:	-	110	136	110
Note: There is one more category for homes, ‘Awareness and Education’ with the points of 3				

Studies, indicated that the GBRTs lay out the project-frameworks for developing green-infrastructure as they are the basic Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)-tools (Cole, 2005). However, some studies have analysed that these GBRTs chiefly rate structures, depending on their environmental-impacts rather than the wholistic-paradigm of sustainability of three ‘P’s. Design and cost, in the context of green and NZE-infrastructure development, are closely interlinked but tools, such as LEED substantially lack the economic-aspect in the rating-process. Moreover, the sustainability-categories decided by the GBRTs differ for every nation, depending on the state of climates, available-resources, economic-development and public-approach. There is a lack of internationally-unified green rating-tools with integrated credit/marketing-systems for similar sustainability-categories (Awadh, 2017).

2.2. Green-Buildings & the Circular Economy

Despite the promotion of green-infrastructure, the modern building-industry is still the largest consumer of the world's natural-resources, causing third of the global waste-generation and landfills (Miller, 2021). The new construction-projects, started after the COVID-19 pandemic, still emit ~3.4 Gigatons of CO₂ while consuming ~40% of raw-materials, globally (UNEP, 2021; Ade and Rehm, 2020; Miller, 2021). Additionally, with the expanding gap between the finite world-resources and its overconsumption, the world needs to find innovative solutions for altering the 'linear-economic' model of 'take, make & dispose'. The estimations have indicated that adapting a circular-economy now, can offer a global economic-opportunity of 4.5 trillion by avoiding construction-waste. Circular-economy efficiently fosters solutions, based on 'reduce, reuse & recycle' (Goyal et al., 2018). It is interlinked with renewable-energy generation as it is a pathway to decarbonization, therefore, an important facet of the net zero-concept.

Figure 13. An Aerial View of Urban-Rigger Model with Twelve Homes with Communal-Space in the Middle, Copenhagen, Denmark (de Carniere and Lyng, 2016)

A circular-economy based student-housing project, called 'Urban Rigger' in Copenhagen, comprises floating and energy-independent homes, made from the discarded shipping-containers, with an easily replicable prototype-design. This sustainable and affordable homes use limited-space to create living-spaces and GBT-installation (Campbell, No Date; Iype, 2019). This project aligns with the principles of circular-economy and several UNSDGs. The benefits of the green buildings in global-economy, building-industry & property-market are constantly growing due to their performance and cost-efficiency (**Fig. 15**) (WGBC, 2022).

Figure 14. A Concept-Based, Inclusive & International Chronological Timeline of the Green Architecture & NZEBs, Showing the Emergence & Evolution of the Field (**Note:** Created by Author from the Timeline-Sources, Mentioned Above)

2.3. World Green Building Council (WGBC) & the NZEBs

Established in 2002, the WGBC is a global non-profit organization (NGO) of the network of more than 69 member-countries with National Green Building Councils & ~36,000 individual-companies to foster green-infrastructure, globally. The framework of this NGO works on three-direction strategies, ‘Climate Action’, ‘Health and Well-Being’ & ‘Resource and Circularity’, aligning with the UNSDGs to ultimately achieve a 100% NZ-carbon building-sector by 2050 (Appendix [A]-5). Presently, the WGBC is working to align its vision with the goal of COP21 (i.e., limiting global temperature increase to 2°C) through adopting the NZE-pathway (WGBC, 2022).

Figure 15. A Graph Showing the Global Market Size of the NZEB by Region in Billion U.S.D., from 2016 to 2028 (Polaris Market Research, 2021)

The GBCs pioneered the concept of high-performance green-buildings, called the NZEBs, that aim to curb the building’s dependency on conventional-resources & promote renewable-energy throughout its lifespan. These buildings are ‘net-zero’ in nature with attributes like high energy-efficiency, cost-efficiency & performance- efficiency (Omrany et al., 2022). The term ‘net zero building’ was first proposed by the Danish researchers, back in 1976, while conducting the research on solar-energy for building-heating during winters (Feng et al., 2019). ‘NZEB’ as a term, has been evolving ever since and has gained wider global attention in the last few years. More recently in the 2000s, with the emergence and expansion of ‘net-zero concept’ in the field of physical climate-science, NZEB has become mainstream in the building-sector (Fankhauser et al., 2021; Shirinbakhsh and Harvey, 2021). It has evolved as a significant ‘mitigation-strategy’ against climate-change. With a clear-growth, the market of the NZEB is rising faster than the conventional-building market, because it is persuasive in terms of profit-making with improved building life-cycle (**Fig. 15**) (Olubunmi et al., 2016).

A NZEB-system comprises a balance-metrics or crediting-system (i.e., generated clean or feed-in energy from the building is equal to delivered-energy from grid), wherein the demand-supply ratio becomes equal. The crediting-system or weighting-system (**Fig. 16**) includes primary-energy usage, total delivered-energy, emissions as well as the costs generated by it (Cao et al, 2016). The 2 types of energy-balancing include: (i) energy demand v/s energy generation (during the designing-stage), (ii) delivered or imported-energy v/s exported energy (in the building’s operation). Annual energy-balancing period with the first balancing type, mentioned is widely used in the NZEBs (Sartori et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2019).

Figure 16. A Diagram Showing the System-Structure of Grid-connected NZEB (Sartori et al., 2012) (Note: For Terminology, See Appendix [A]-6)

Figure 17. A Hierarchy of Possible NZEB-Designs with Different Energy-Infrastructure and Resources: Option 0- Energy-Efficient Design through Passive Design Features; Option 1- On-site Energy-Infrastructure; Option 2- On-site, Nearby-Energy Infrastructure; Option 3- On-site Energy-Production with Off-site Microgenerating Techniques; Option 4- Off-site Energy-Production (Torcellini et al., 2006)

There are two types of NZEB: ‘grid connected’ & ‘stand-alone’; The first is connected to the main energy-infrastructure and the second is autonomous in nature with adequate storage-

capacity for the generated-energy for the building’s internal-usage. The self-reliant, stand-alone NZEBs have gained more attention in rural or remote-regions without a direct access to the main-grid (Cao et al, 2016; Liu et al., 2019). Although Keele represents a rural-campus, the presented case-study will focus on the ‘grid-connected NZEB’ (Fig. 16).

2.3.1. NZEB-Development: A Broad International Scenario

Indicators show the rise of 32% and 16% in the world’s overall energy-consumption & CO₂-emissions from the years 2012 to 2035, respectively (Cao et al, 2016). In the last decade, many nations pledged to curtail their fossil-fuels usage, aligning with the UNSDGs, the global ‘net zero targets’ of Paris Agreement to ‘*limit the world’s temperature well-below 2°C*’. As a part of which, most nations formed targets to transform their building-sector and promote development towards the ‘NZ-infrastructure’ (Table 6) (Omrany et al., 2022). The UK was among the first nations to mandate NZEB-implementation to construct all new houses with net zero-carbon status & all new non-residential buildings from 2016 and 2019, respectively, under the Zero Carbon Building Policy (Table 6) (UKGBC, 2022). Whereas, the large energy-consuming counties like China and India are relatively late to frame and implement NZE-infrastructure targets and policies. China developed ~5000 NZEBs in 2020 and the market is rapidly growing (Liu et al., 2019). India recorded >10,000 new, large-scale commercial-retrofits in 2020 and has a further commitment to reduce 50% of its energy-consumption by 2030 in the commercial building-sector (Saini et al., 2022) through the NZE-pathway.

Table 6(continued). A List of Various Approaches Towards the NZ-Buildings in Different Nations with Their Legislation and Implementation-Target Years (Omrany et al., 2022) (Note: See Appendix [A]-5)

Nation	Year of Legislation	Target & Target Year	Target or Set Goal	Approach Towards the NZEBs
U.K.	04/2007	2016	Each newly-built dwelling must reach net zero carbon	<i>“A building with net zero production of CO₂ from every type of energy-use in the house, over the year.”</i>
Federal Government of the U.S.A.	12/2007	2040	About 50% of the commercial building-projects, to reach NZEB across the nation and by 2050 all should reach the NZEB status	<i>“A built-space with minimal energy requirements and use, that is generated from a resource with minimum to no GHGs-emission while making all commercials set-ups economically-efficient and viable in the country.”</i>
U.S.A. NASA & USGBC Roadmap	01/2010	2020	All (newly-built) NASA projects will reach NZEB-target	<i>“From the building’s planning, a NZEB sets up an aggressive-energy usage intensity target, after which it meets the goal of reduced-energy through novel GBTs, energy efficient technologies and finally, it produces clean-energy to offset the yearly conventional or non-renewable energy-usage of the building.”</i>

Australia	02/2019	2030	All commercial & residential build-spaces must reach net zero energy carbon state	<i>“The ‘NZE and Carbon’ buildings are the buildings with energy-efficient thermal-envelope and smart appliances that uses low-energy. These building set-ups are suitable for on or off-site renewable-energy set-ups to generate clean energy and reach net-zero.”</i>
The EU	05/2010	2021	Every new construction-project must reach nearly- ‘Net Zero’ target	<i>“A nearly net-zero building with high energy-performance that involves on-site or nearby renewable energy-generating resource.”</i> (This definition and concept in the context of various EU member-states differ slightly, however, the ultimate target of each concept is to achieve ‘net-zero state’ in the future.)
Japan	04/2014	2050	All new residential-projects must reach net zero emissions	<i>“Building with an annual net zero primary-energy consumption.”</i>

The global-interest in NZEBs has been increasing constantly since 2006 but it consists huge differences in the developmental-approached in various regions. ~90% of the NZEB-projects are based in developed-states like the EU and U.S.A., where the field is presently growing rapidly due to the R&D-programmes and comprehensive policy-frameworks (Liu et al., 2019; Ohene et al., 2022). This imbalance indicates a striking difference between the economic, academic-resources and policy-regulations of the developing and developed-nations. Financial-constraints like high initial-investment and lack of sufficient green-funding also play key role in the growth of NZEBs. However, the advancements in renewable energy-technologies have played a huge part in the field. The World’s total primary-energy generation from renewables has accounted for 13.47% in 2021 (Ritchie et al, 2022) (Appendix [B]-2). However, the NZEB’s ‘zero energy-evaluation’ is based on the performance-indicators like energy-consumption. its intensity in kWh/year in the building. The NZEBs generate on or off-site clean-energy, on which the concept of yearly-reduction in electricity is based. This performance-evaluation, however, does not consider the GHGs released before achieving the net zero energy-status (i.e., construction, renovation etc.). Therefore, the building may not reach or maintain the net zero energy-status throughout the building-lifespan (Jain and Rawal, 2022).

2.4. The State-of-the-Art of the Selected GBTs

The GBTs are promising offshoot-technologies of the green building-sector, that have advanced over the last 2 decades. They align with the UNSDG-framework and therefore, act as the drivers of sustainable-development (Darko et al., 2017). Innovations like high-efficiency solar-PVs, geothermal-floor and water heating-systems, latest wind-turbines are the building-blocks of the green-infrastructure (Deng at al., 2014). Its market-growth has affected the ZE

and green building-sector development across the globe. To reach the global NZ-target by 2050, the world needs to triple the investment (\$4 trillion) in renewables (EIA, 2021). The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) has launched a roadmap to increase the share of renewable-energy in the global energy-mix by 2030 as renewables are the key sustainability-solutions. However, each nation has developed a roadmap with specific-targets to NZ energy-infrastructure to make the building-sector energy-efficient (**Table 6**) (**Fig. 18**). Currently, the cooperation of renewables and passive design-measures with the existing-structures is widely accepted but with the smart-grid development, buildings can become 100% self-reliant in the future (Deng et al., 2014; Wu and Skye, 2021).

Figure 18. A Common Strategic Roadmap Framework for Achieving Net Zero Energy Infrastructure through Greening the Building-Sector (Redrawn after Deng et al., 2014)

Presently, China (2185TWh), U.S.A (1402 TWh), EU (1069 TWh) and India (315 TWh) are leading in the global renewable energy-market (Ritchie et al, 2022). Indicators show that the market-size of the renewables will grow from 952.16 USD in 2021 to 1,998.03 USD in 2030 (IRENA, 2022). Solar & wind energy-technologies can be installed and/or retrofitted on and/or off-site but have cons, such as a limited harvesting-period, noise-pollution and shadow-flickering impacts. Despite the barriers, new technologies have emerged and have a huge possibility of further future-growth (Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2020; Wu and Skye, 2021). To, date there are numerous advancements in GBTs, which make their systematic evaluation complex at the global-scale. The following section attempts to analyse the state-of-the-art of the selected GBTs (i.e. here, renewable energy technologies) for the presented case-study.

2.4.1. Solar-Photovoltaic (PV)

2.4.1.1. Present Global Scenario

The first solar power-station in the 1980s, had a built-capacity of over 1MW, after which the installed-capacity of the solar-PVs has gradually increased (**Fig. 19**) (Binz et al., 2017). The world’s solar-PV generation in 2020 accounted for 821 TWh, which will achieve 24% of average yearly growth by 2030. With the increase in installed-capacity, the solar-PV costs have constantly declined over the years and will further experience a reduction of ~59% by 2025 (**Figure 20**) (EIA, 2021; IRENA, 2021). The UK has increased its cumulative installed solar-PV capacity from 95 megawatts in 2010 to 13,965 megawatts in 2021 with over one million sites, that generate electricity from solar-PVs (Jaganmohan, 2021).

Figure 19. A Graph Showing the Global Solar PV Cumulative Capacity in Megawatts from 1996 to 2021 (Ritchie and Roser, 2022) (Note: See, Appendix [A]-7)

Figure 20. A Graph Showing a Drop in the Global Average Prices in US\$ per Watt of Solar PV Modules from 1976 to 2019 (Ritchie and Roser, 2022) (Note: See, Appendix [A]-8)

2.4.1.2. Innovations and Advances

Solar-PVs easily generate electrical-energy from the solar-energy through the photoelectric-effect. On-site solar-PV systems presently dominate the market of GBTs in NZEBs-development because a large area of the incident solar radiation (G_g) on the PV-surface is converted from solar to thermal-energy, which increases the working-area and temperature of the solar-PVs (Wu and Skye, 2021, Cao et al, 2016). With the improvements in solar-cells, the PV-efficiency has also increased (i.e., ranges from 10 to ~39%) over time (Pandey et al., 2016; Ng and Mithraratne, 2014).

The installation/retrofit-areas for solar-PVs include: (i) ground-mounted solar-PVs for off-site or nearby-generation, (ii) rooftop/terrace, windows and walls for on-site generation, enlarging the building's surface-area for harnessing solar-power. Rooftop/terrace mounts are the most common in NZEB-development as on-site systems are readily available, easily installable. Besides, they reduce the overall material and construction-costs while efficiently using the

space and make the buildings energy-independent. On-site PVs have two subsets: Building integrated solar-PV systems (BIPV) and Building-Applied PVs (BAPV), from which the first-type currently dominates the commercial PV-market (Kumar et al., 2019; Wu and Skye, 2021). The BIPV-market size was 1.9 billion U.S.D. in 2020, that will grow to 88.38 billion U.S.D. with a market CAGR of 20.7% by 2030 (Grand View Research, 2022).

Table 7. Different Solar PV-Systems, Specifications & Current Market-Size (See, **Fig. 21**)

Solar-PV Systems	Remark on the Current State	Limitations
BIPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PV-modules are directly installed as the external-side of the roofs/facades/walls/windows or cladding, replacing the conventional building-materials to reduce overall construction-cost. - Can also be retrofitted on an existing structure but are usually part of the building-envelope (i.e., built during the construction-phase) - Gained popularity in recent years due to its cost and energy-efficient nature. - Significantly decreases the building-load for heating and/or cooling by the shading effect - Semi to fully transparent in nature; shorter pay-back period <p>Sources: (Ng and Mithraratne, 2014; Peng et al., 2013; Lu et al., 2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -High upfront cost -BIPVs cost higher in countries with small PV-markets -Requires Skilled architects, designers and installers with good knowledge of BIPVs & special building designs/plans -Large buildings may have long pay-back periods. <p>Source: (Lu et al., 2019)</p>
BAPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -PV-modules are directly retrofitted/installed on the exteriors of building-roofs, facades, walls, terraces. - Suitable for & widely popular in residential building sector. -PVs are installed/retrofitted on slant and horizontal surfaces to optimize the energy productivity. - Not as productive as the BIPVs but have relatively less maintenance-cost, once retrofitted. -Rooftop BAPV systems: highest contributing systems. -Its market size of BAPV is estimated rise with the CAGR of around 7.23% with a market-value of ~551.13 U.S.D. by 2028. However, the BIPVs are taking over the market of solar PVs with a number of breakthroughs in solar cell types, design and efficiency. <p>Sources: (Kumar et al., 2019; Wu and Skye, 2021; Maximize Market Research, 2022)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -High initial cost, depending on the size of the PV-system/s -Long-term replacement costs -It affects the buildings external outlook. <p>Source: (Kumar et al., 2019)</p>

Figure 21(continued). (a) Difference between the BIPV & BAPV systems (Qcells, 2021) (b) A View of Grid-Connected BIPV & BAPV systems (Kumar et al., 2019)

Currently, combined solar-energy systems like solar PV/T are utilized for **space**-heating, cooling in countries with extreme-weather, where reaching NZE-state is difficult due to the high-loads (Wu and Skye, 2021). The PV/Ts are costlier than the PV and/or solar-thermal systems and comprise numerous technical-issues regarding the building's design, requirement, installation and system-efficiency. The market size of PV/Ts is relatively small in comparison with other PV-technologies but glazed PV/T systems are highly-efficient as they simultaneously yield electricity and heat by preventing excessive heat-loss. However, studies show that structures with conventional-PVs are highly likely to achieve NZE-status in shorter time-frame as compared to PV/Ts. This is because climates affect PV/T's efficiency and it gives less output during darker/rainy days or in low sun-light (Good et al., 2015, Diwania et al., 2020).

Local geography & climate-patterns highly influence the productivity of solar-PVs. Tropical-regions with high average annual-temperatures, solar-irradiation (H) & uniform-climates are more suitable for solar-technologies. However, the PV-field has advanced significantly over the last two-decades. Advanced weather-forecast systems, high-efficiency solar-cells (**Table 8**), unique solar-PV innovations with sun-tracking devices (**Table 9**) have revolutionized the PV-field (Cao et al, 2016).

Advances in solar-cell in recent decades have provided diversity in PV-applications (**Fig. 22**). Semiconducting material-made high-performance and cost-efficient crystalline silicon (c-Si)-cells dominate the PV-market. ~23 to 30% of the research cover studies involving the c-Si (Diwania et al., 2020). However, recently, the American National Renewable Energy Laboratory conducted research in '*six PV-layered solar-cells, fabricated with alloys of III-V semiconductors with ~47.1% of efficiency*', that are economically more feasible than the c-Si. Here, each PV-layers absorbs specific-portion of the light-spectrum & combined with CPVs can reach ~50% of more working-efficiency while occupying less space (Geisz al., 2020). All global-customers now expect multinational to enhance their of environmental-responsibility, thus commercial, non-residential giants have considered PV-innovations for decreasing their emissions (Schwarzenegger, 2014). Despite the present high-costs, PV-technologies will gain wider-adaptation in the NZE and green building-sector in the future due to the dropping prices & growing energy-demand.

Figure 22. A Classification Diagram of Solar-Cell Technologies (Diwania et al., 2020)
(Note: See Appendix [A]-9 for Specifications)

Table 8. A Table Listing High-Efficiency Advanced Solar-cell technologies

Type of Solar PV-cell	Overall Efficiency Remark
Pervoskite Solar cells (Diwania et al., 2020; Ferrell, 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A hybrid solar-cell with crystalline materials (i.e., mineral CaTiO₃ or Calcium Titanium Oxide). - Very high-efficiency (i.e., ~25 to 30%) - Cost-efficient as they are cheaper than c-Si in terms of production cost - Made through solution-processing, thus, absorbs wide range of wavelengths of the sun-light - Constructed as thin-film (TF), for achieving space-efficiency, therefore, are considered as a new future option of the PV industry
Concentrated PV-Cells (CPV) (Pandey et al., 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An advanced solar-technology with optical tools like concave or curved lenses to focus harness more solar-power onto a smaller-area - Highly cost & performance-efficient - Low initial investment as compared to other technologies (i.e., by providing initial cost-predictability) - Take up less space than the flat PV-systems - High-CPVs efficiency: 30-40%
Organic Solar Cell (Smith and Nelson, 2022; Pandey et al., 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low cost, cutting-edge technology with very high-performance efficiency and high mechanical-flexibility - Low manufacturing costs with solution-process - semi-transparent outlook, light in weight and made with organic-semiconductors - Flexible for colour-tuning and thus can be deposited on various substrates to create aesthetically appealing outlook Efficiency is usually more than 18% with a lifespan of over 12-years
Polymer Solar Cells (Pandey et al., 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A recently developed low-cost technology with a great range of diversity in semi-conducting polymer materials. - Manufactured with solution-processing methods. - Flexible, semi-transparent technologies and light-wight - With a very thin active layer (i.e., ~250-255 nm) of thickness, which is much lesser than the conventional silicon-based solar-cells - Overall working efficiency is over 15-16%

Table 9. A Table Listing Some of the Most Advanced Solar-PV Innovations & Designs

Solar-Innovations	Remarks on Functional & Economic Aspects
Solar Trees (Hyder et al., 2018; Spotlight Solar, No Date; Almadhhachi et al, 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ground-mounted, tree-shaped solar-PV sculptures with a metallic-trunk, branches & solar-PV leaves that take up to only 1-2 % of the ground-space in comparison with the mounted/retrofitted flat-PVs, solar-trees - A feasible option for on-site power-generation - Mostly stand-alone with storage-batteries and inverters but can be connected to the grid - Produce 5 to 10% of more power than the roof/terrace mounted PVs, depending on the leaves-orientation
Solar Smart-Flowers (Schwarzenegger, 2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A cutting-edge PV-technology with floral-structure, comprising 10-12 high efficiency PV-petals in a circular/disc-format for power-generation - Stan-alone structures with batteries, inverters, automated internal cleaning mechanism (ACS) & sun-tracking device -The rooftop flowers can harness up to 6,250 kWh (i.e., location, Rome, Italy) with a two-axis tracking-mechanism, in each direction to 90° angle - It harnesses 40-50% more energy than the conventional roof-top PV-systems that can work in extreme temperature range - High installation cost, however, highly efficient for commercial-settings
Agri-voltaic (Sax, 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -A hybrid PV-technology, combing agriculture and solar-energy generation by harvesting edible, commercially important plants under and near the solar-PVs (i.e., solar PV-roofs/shades and solar-fences, respectively) -The harvested energy can be directly used in the farming-sector or sold - The plants are selected according to PVs'-design & movements. PV-shades reduce over-evaporation processes. This symbiotic relationship reduces space and water consumption in agriculture - High initial-cost but its market is estimated to grow to ~40% by 2025
Floatovoltaic or Floating PVs (Sax, 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water-reservoir based floatovoltaic-farm with floating PV-rafts & ongoing aquaculture to harness solar-energy - This technique reduces 30-40% of water-evaporation, therefore, is suitable for water-deficient with low annual precipitation - Reduces blue-green algae contamination in the water, thus, lower the costs of water treatment. - Oceanic floatovoltaics are 13% more efficient than the inland-farms - Presently limited to a few regions because of the development-costs but will be practically feasible by the next upcoming-decade - Suitable for nearby or off-site generation

2.4.2. Wind Energy-Technologies

2.4.2.1.Present Global Scenario

Non-stationary, highly unpredictable in nature, wind is a source of clean-energy with regular variations in energy-generating process. The world's wind-energy generation has increased from <0.01 TWh in 1978 to in 1813.70 TWh in 2021. Its present market-value accountd for \$99.28 billion but it will grow rapidly by 2030 with a CAGR of 6.5%. Presently, China (614.18 TWh), U.S.A. (379.77 TWh) and India (68.08 TWh) are leading in this field, globally (Ritchie et al., 2022).

Figure 23. Global Wind-Energy Generation in TWh by Region in 2021 (Ritchie et al., 2022)

2.4.2.2. HAWTs & VAWTs: Technological-Advances

All utility-scale modern Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs: turbines with horizontal blade-rotation axis) comprise 2-3 aerodynamic-blades, that are connected to the rotor. When the winds hit the turbine-blades, an aerodynamic lift-force is generated, that allows the rotor to rotate. This rotation is then transferred from low to high-speed shaft by a gear-box, which increases the original low speed-rotations to high speed-rotations. Finally, this mechanical-energy is converted to electrical-energy by the generator. In recent year, HAWTs with mono or multiple (6-12)-blades are also developed for various commercial-proposes (Hyams, 2012). Offshore wind-energy farms with giant HAWTs are gaining wider consideration in the field for large-scale generation. This is possible due to the advances like taller turbine-towers and increased blade-size.

Netherlands has developed the world’s first ‘Haliade X offshore turbines (HAWT)’ with 14MW of generation-capacity and capacity-factor of 60-64%, that can generate power even at lower wind-speeds. This turbine-tower is 260 m-tall with a 107 m, 220 m of glade & rotor-diameter, respectively (General Electric, 2022). Siemens Gamesa, a leading global clean-energy industry has launched 81 m-long, recyclable turbine-blades and will launch a fully-recyclable wind-turbine by 2040. These blade-materials comprise numerous resins and composite-materials, that can entere the circular-economy to reach suppliers after the turbines’ working-span (Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy, 2021). Long wind-turbines with recyclable-blades will not only harness more energy, reduce overall energy-generation costs but also promote zero-waste approach & stimulate the clean-energy market for recycled-materials in the future (Schupak, 2021).

However, energy-generation through HAWTs is highly influenced by turbine-capacity, blade-radius, wind-speed & air-density. Moreover, it has multiple disadvantages like their huge-scale, unesthetic-outlook, high maintenance-costs, neighbourhod-design, mono-directionality, requirement of optimal weather-conditions and noise-pollution. Presently, medium to small-scale HAWTs with different designs and orientations are widely utilized in space-deficient areas (i.e., urban-areas) (Fig. 24).

Figure 24. Types of small-HAWTs (a) Swift, (b) Eclectic, (c) Fortis Montana, (d) Scirocco (Redrwan after Ishugah et al., 2014) (**Note:** See **Table 10**)

Table 10. A Table, Showing the Types of Small to Medium-Scale HAWT Designs (Ishugah et al., 2014; Hyams, 2012)

HAWT Design	Main Features	Main Purpose
Swift	4 or more small blades with a circular, peripheral rim to decrease the noise-pollution (Noise level: ≤ 35 Decibel)	Ideal, small-scale HAWTs for installation on rooftops of non-residential buildings/homes, especially in urban and semi-urban areas.
Eclectic	5-balded HAWT with high efficiency, efficiently work in lower wind-speeds	Suitable for urban, semi-urban areas.
Fortis Montana	The most suitable type of HAWT for buildings as it produces minimal to no noise (i.e., no more than 3 Decibel)	Small dimensions with a building-friendly size, especially for homes.
Scirocco	Large in size with 2 rotor-blades with high efficiency	Cost and energy-efficient, designed for homes and commercial buildings for low to medium-scale generation.

The global-installed wind-power capacity accounted for 837 gigawatts in 2021 and it is estimated to grow to 6000 gigawatts by 2050 (IRENA, 2019). In addition to large-scale generation, wind-energy is also harnessed by small wind-turbines. Wind-energy generation in non-commercial sectors has two chief-approaches, that can be found in the existing literature: (i) inland wind-farms in city/towns' peripheries and open-spaces outside the city/town (ii) energy-generation through building-integrated or small-scale wind turbines, called Vertical Axis Wind Turbines (VAWTs) (Ishugah et al., 2014).

Presently, the VAWTs are gaining wider non-commercial interest as they are suitable for on-site microgeneration for NZEBs (Zhao et al., 2022). The costs of wind-power have also constantly decreased over the years and it has now become one of the major competitive-RETs in the global energy-mix. The cost-reduction in wind-technologies is majorly due to the novel designs i.e., the turbine-designs with larger rotor sweeping area (A) & increased hub-heights (Bortolotti et al., 2019). Presently, the rotor-diameter & generation-capacity of the VAWTs ranges from 3-10 m & 1.4-20 kW, respectively (Wu and Skye, 2021). The generation-capacity of the VAWTs is notably lesser than the HAWTs, thus, HAWTs are more practical-options for large non-commercial as well as commercial NZE-structures (i.e. off-site generation). However, VAWTs in dense, urban and space-deficient areas have gained wider attraction as they can be installed/retrofitted on the building rooftops, terraces, facades and/or close to the buildings. VAWTs have blades, following the vertical-axis, which makes them multidirectional in nature. VAWTs can operate in winds, blowing from any direction,

producing minimum to no noise. Moreover, the maintenance-cost of VAWTs'-farm is lesser than the HAWT-farms due to their small size and lower elevation of installation (Ishugah et al., 2014).

Figure 25. Different Types of VAWTs: (a) Savonius, (b) Darrieus or D-Type, (c) H-Blade Type (d) Helix or Helical-Type (e) Tulipo or Tulip (Castellani et al., 2019; Ishugah et al., 2014) (Note: See Table 11)

Table 11(continued). A Table, Showing the Types of VAWT-Designs (Castellani et al., 2019; Zilberman, 2017; Elcprocus, 2022)

VAWTs	Remark
Savonius	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed with 2 or more, scoop-like half cylinders or container - The transverse-section of the turbine looks like letter-‘S’ - One of the simplest types of VAWTs and is generally the least efficient than other VAWTs, as it works on the principle of drag-forces - Can operate with low wind-speed with very low noise and vibration, thus, suitable for building-installations (Source: Castellani et al., 2019)
Darrieus or D-Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usually more efficient than the former one as it operates on the principle of lift-forces; Created suction over the face-sides by the winds, generate force to revolve the turbines - Operated on the low-torque, which can achieve the efficiency of 30-40%, generating sufficient energy for a small-to-medium sized house - Designed with 2, 3 or more curved-blades - Mainly designed for open-spaces or moderately high-rooftops to generate electricity (Source: Castellani et al., 2019; Zilberman, 2017; Elcprocus, 2022)
H-Blade Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed after the prototyping process of Darrieus VAWTs - Usually comprise 3 or more straight vertical blades of similar length, where the junction or struts connects these blades to the main shaft or central mast - Low manufacturing and installation cost due to their simple design - Have good performance-efficiency (Source: Alqurashi and Mohamed 2020)

Helix or Helical-Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Darrius-type turbines with twisted or helical design with two to three curved-blades, joined with the shaft - The helical designs create low vibration, noise (around 40-50 decibel) & minimal to no shadow-flickering with no visual disturbance, while operating even in the slow wind-speed - Specially designed for the buildings and can be retrofitted on high rooftops (Source: Castellani et al., 2019; Reza, et al., 2015; Zilberman, 2017).
Tulipo or Tulip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High performance with low maintenance-costs; Noiseless turbines with the shape of small tulip-bud - No visual-disturbance due to the enclosed blades but have relatively low generation-capacity - Remarkably cost-efficient, thus, suitable for rooftop (Source: Ishugah et al., 2014).

As the number of small-scale NZEB-pilot projects & decentralized applications are increasing, the global market-size of VAWTs is predicted to be \$16,115.9 million by the year 2028 with a CAGR of 4.2% (i.e., from 2021-2028) (Zion Market Research, 2022). Studies, conducted to date have indicated that the wind-turbines can harness more energy for a NZEB (i) when retrofitted/installed by following the policy-guidance for each geographical-region, considering factors like average wind-speed, wind-flow direction, building-size and available space (ii) when retrofitted on the high-ceilings or vaulted-roofs (i.e., with a capacity factor of >50%). The first approach is commonly adopted in many states but the growing NZEB-market has widened the scopes of VAWTs' future-growth (Abohela et al., 2013; Cao et al., 2016).

2.5. Vertical Greenery System (VGS): Green Facades

Urban heat island effect and prolonged periods of intense-heat became some of the main issues of the modern-world, thus, the concept of passive design features was introduced with the rise and development of modern-architecture. Later, all modern green building designs incorporated these features in order to provide the buildings with natural insulation for cooling & heating. The traditional practice of greening the building's vertical-facades was reshaped to develop the passive architectural practice, called vertical greenery system (VGS). The motto of the early VGS in modern-architecture was to provide natural insulation through plants to the buildings without technological-devices. The studies, focusing on various types and themes of VGS has enhanced from 25% to 60% in the last decade (Bustami et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2010) with numerous advancements and novel techniques. VGS is the practice of cultivating plants on the buildings vertical-walls or green-facades, that is also called bio-shader, vertical-gardening or farming and/or vertical-landscaping (safikhani et al., 2014).

There are two main-categories of VGS on the basis of construction and outlook: (a) single or double-skinned green-facades, (b) vertical green (living)-walls (**Fig. 34**). The first refers to the vegetation-cover through the plants (i.e., usually creepers, climbers and vines) grown adjacent to the building-surface, that flourishes to sheath the entire wall/façade. The installation, development and long-term maintenance of this technique is less-laborious & is usually practiced for high-walls (5-≥9 m) and long-term development (i.e., life-span of 50-60 years). With the direct-type, the climbers directly climb the adjacent-building walls & with the indirect type plants climb on the strings or metal-cables, attached to the building-walls (Perez et al., 2014; Bustami et al., 2018). Whereas, living-walls consist the columns of durable plastic-containers or high-density polyethylene planters-pots, attached to walls with an aligned watering-system, hydroponics. There are 3 sub-types of living-walls: modular, simple felt/panels/rods & horizontal-felt (**Fig. 34**). Built outdoors or indoors, these are more diverse and versatile VGS-practices as various herbs, small-shrubs can be cultivated here but its

installation and maintenance are more time and laborious-intensive (Eumorfopoulou & Kontoleon, 2009; Bustami et al., 2018).

VGSs are used as both active and passive-features of heating, ventilation & air-conditioning (HVAC)-systems in energy-saving buildings, but the difference between the two is that the active-systems comprise an air-flowing ventilator, either on the top, adjacent or bottom of the vertical-garden, that blows air across the substrate of the foliage. Subsequently, the air-temperature is lowered by the transpiration-process of the plants, that improves the indoor air-temperature. Whereas, the passive-systems do not comprise external cooling (i.e., extra-biofiltration) but only operates through the natural air-flow (safikhani et al., 2014).

The prolonged sun-exposure along with many other climate-factors heightens the building temperature. Plants in the VGS act as solar-barriers or curtains and prevents excessive heat-absorption by the building as the green foliage absorb solar-radiation for its physiological-functioning like photosynthesis, transpiration, respiration. The VGS can notably reduce the building-temperature to 10-12°C with the drop of 3-3.5°C in the ambient-temperature, nearby the building (Wong et al., 2010). Besides maintaining the thermal-comfort, foliage prevents extreme wind effect and maintain the humidity of the building-interior. Here, the symbiotic relationship between the plants and the buildings establishes an array of benefits from improving the building-outlook, its internal air-quality, insulation, environmental-performance to attracting the local-biodiversity and supporting the ecosystem. Previous studies have shown that VGS, as the external building-envelope, significantly reduces the buildings heating & cooling period, especially in dense and urban-areas (Eumorfopoulou & Kontoleon, 2009), therefore, reducing the buildings energy-use for heating (i.e., by evapotranspiration) and cooling (i.e., by foliage-shading). In other words, the higher the 'leaf-area-index' (i.e., leaf-surface area), the better the thermal-behaviour of the VGS. Moreover, previous studies have shown that it adds value to the building's green-benchmarking and occupants well-being. As passive-features, the VGS in energy-buildings are highly depended on local climatic-conditions and system-type. The performance or thermal-behaviour of the VGS depends on local seasonal-patterns, solar-exposure, humidity-levels, precipitation and frost as well as the type, density, thickness, phyllotaxy of the foliage & VGS-design (Perez et al., 2014). Yet, the studies on plant-species for different climates, system-classifications in terms of local climates and the thermal-behaviour of certain widely-used foliage have not been rigorously studied. Some, recent studies have shown that the integrated systems like water-reuse & VGS with crop-production can be cost and optimally energy efficient in energy-saving buildings (Perez et al., 2014). Resistant and visually attractive plant-species with open-phyllotaxy and good foliage-density, are usually selected for the VGSs, depending on the local-climates. Perennial, annual herbs, climbers and creepers, grass species, ornamental foliage like succulents and wall-shrubs are selected for a range of climates, worldwide (Manso and Castro-Gomes, 2015).

The field has evolved towards finding the solutions of various designs and VGSs with light-weight, recycled and low-maintenance materials. Yet, the most recent studies still focus on the metallic or mesh-based modular VGSs. With the evolution in the global-architecture, the forms of pre-existing VGSs must change (i.e., curved, vertical panels etc), incorporating automated-sensors for watering, nutrients, however, these areas still need deeper understanding and development, globally (Manso and Castro-Gomes, 2015).

Overall, the field of the NZEB has developed significantly over the last two decades with numerous green or renewable technological-advances & natural energy-saving passive measures. Presently, solar and wind, together, contribute significantly to on-site, small-scale

generation in the NZE-structures through numerous cutting-edge advances with improved system-efficiency. The next chapter provides a closer look into the investigation of the GBTs energy production and operation.

3. Methodology

With the case study-based research approach, the proposed-research aimed to investigate the viability of the transformation of the CB at Keele University into a functional-NZEB by theoretically or conceptually retrofitting various GBTs (**Table 12**) and introducing a passive design aspect to produce clean-energy, that equals to the CB’s annual energy-demand profile. Secondly, it aimed to analyse the estimation-based yearly water-demand profile of the CB by reviewing previous literature. With a ‘quantitative methodological-approach’, the proposed-research was carried out, using multiple quantitative data-collection methods and various types of quantitative-data, as mentioned in (**Fig. 27**), (**Table 13**).

Table 12. A Table of Selected Green Building Technologies (GBTs) & a Passive Design Feature for Proposed Research-Project

GBTs & Total Number of Retrofits	Purpose
1. Roof-Top/Terrace Mounted High Efficiency Solar-PVs (Total 82)	Renewable Energy Technologies (RETs) to harness clean energy (i.e., solar and wind energy) from the natural resources and reduce emissions.
2. Solar-PV Trees (Total 8)	
3. Wind Turbine (VAWTs) (Total 16)	
Passive Design Feature	Purpose
1. Green Façade Development	For vertical greening of all external/front facades of the CBA (excluding the café & kitchen-areas) to provide a good building-outlook and thermal-comfort

3.1. Research Methodology & Research Framework

Conventionally, the case-study research-approach is usually linked to the ‘qualitative research-methodologies’ as it is descriptive in nature and conducts detailed exploration of a specific aspect/s of the research-area. However, this can accommodate various formal or non-formal statistical-methods (Gerring, 2007; Rashid et al., 2019). The qualitative methodological-approach for the case-studies often lack a comprehensive methodological rigour and research objectivity. In other words, qualitative methodologies may not comprehensively describe the objective-operations like mathematical-analysis for empirical research, as they are substantially based on the qualitative-data like observational-values, narratives etc (Wills, 2014). Some previous studies indicated that the qualitative-research can be transformed to a quantitative-research with numerous statistical-techniques. However, it would be difficult to interpret this transformed-findings or data without the underlying narratives of the fundamental qualitative-research (Ochieng, 2009). The presented case-study, therefore, incorporated a ‘quantitative methodological-approach’ in order to address the set objectives and aims that focused on the CB’s theoretical-transformation into a NZEB by elucidating various parameters of the research-area. This was because the CB’s conceptual-transformation to a NZEB relied on a number of existing and pre-derived or pre-compiled data as well as analytical and/or statistical-information.

The proposed-research undertook an inductive-approach (i.e., bottom-up approach), first to discover or collect the data, second, to explore the collected-data & third, to analyse the

collected-data (i.e., from data-collection to problem-solving) (Jebb, 2017). This led the research to an ‘exploratory data-analysis method-(EDA)’, explained later in this chapter. This chapter provides a strategic-framework to explain the step-by-step methods, undertaken to collect and analyse the data for the proposed-research (**Fig. 26**).

Continued...

Figure 26. Strategic Research-Framework for the Proposed-research (Created by Author)

3.2. Research-Exploration & Data-Exploration

3.2.1. Data-Collection Methods

With the establishment of research aims, objectives and research-approach, the research-exploration, first, initiated the data-exploration process in order to address the set objective-1 for data-collection (**Figure 26**: step 1). The ‘quantitative data-collection’ method was adopted for acquiring primary and secondary-data. This was because the overall research-objectives majorly focused on the data with specific attributes, such as statistical and/or numerical-information to achieve the research-aims. This quantitative data-collection method combined 2 specific categories: (i) existing data-collection, (ii) compiled or derived data-collection. The first refers to the collection of pre-existing primary and/or secondary-data, whereas, the second refers to the data, derived or extracted from the existing-data to reproduce or generate new data (DeWitt Wallace Library, 2021). These two methods collected data, specifically to address the set objectives-2 & 3. These objectives incorporated an array of data for the selected samples or GBTs. Although, there are various other quantitative data-collection methods for the case-study based empirical-research, such as ‘observational data-collection’ (Hox, and Boeije, 2005), the two, mentioned above, were constructively adapted for the proposed case-study (**Figure 27**). These methods allowed the research to incorporate tabulated and graphically-represented details, based on quantified-data & led it to the findings, chiefly based on objectively-defined and real-world information instead of the opinions and narratives, that are more subjective and ambiguous in nature (Wills, 2014).

Figure 27. A Diagram of Various Types of Data & Selected Data Collection Methods for the Proposed Case-Study (Created by Author) (**Note:** See **Table 13**)

Table 13. Types of Data & Data Collection-Methods, Adopted for the Presented Case-Study (Edited after DeWitt Wallace Library, 2021) (**Note:** See **Figure 27**)

Type of Data & Data Collection Method	Data Gathering Process	Collected Data	Data Resource
Existing Data Collection: Primary (1°) Data	Clicking Pictures, Web-Surfing and Creating Graphical-Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital screengrabs from Goggle Earth with location co-ordinates, photographs of the CB's exterior & its internal spaces - Graphs, tables, edited images and diagrams 	Author
Existing Data Collection: Secondary (2°) Data	Document Review & Emailing: Collecting formerly existing data from university.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building Specification Data includes the digital-maps of the selected location (the CB, Keele University, UK) - Total area-cover of different levels or floors, total number of internal spaces & total annual energy consumption of the CB (Keele Estate Team) & - Images and Keele University's digital map (Keele University Official Webpage) 	Keele Estate Team & Keele University Official Webpage
Existing Data Collection: Secondary (2°) Data	Document Review: Collecting formerly existing data, information, facts, literature by web-browsing & reviewing	- Literature and Visuals (i.e., Images, Graphs)	Websites, Reports, Books, Reports, Journal and Media Articles
Compiled or Derived Data Collection: Secondary (2°) Data	Document Review: Collecting formerly compiled or derived data & information-points by web-browsing, reviewing & directly emailing	- All the climate and weather information for the selected location & UK	UK Met-Office, Global Climate Atlas, Journal Articles
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specifications of GBTs, like system size, efficiency, capacity etc - Mathematical formulas to analyse the energy-output of selected GBTs - Online software for solar-power generation calculations 	Web-Pages of Mentioned GBT-Companies and/or Organizations and/or industry
		- Data of the water-use of large-buildings (i.e., here, institutional large building)	The EIA Webpage

The proposed-research embodied a probability sampling-approach (Berndt, 2020) for the quantitative data-collection methods, wherein the samples referred to a specific GBT or groups of GBTs & a passive design technique (**Table 12**) from all the existing NZEB-technologies. This approach allowed the research to consider and collect specific data-sets, technical-information and its key aspects of selected samples (i.e., GBTs) from the entire sets of available and/or published data. The resources, chosen for the secondary-data collection were the prime data-depositories/data-base/data-providers, involving all types of secondary-data, required for the research as shown in (**Table 13**).

3.2.2. Types of Data & Data-Collection Resources

Quantitative methodological approaches usually include more than one data-collection resources, depending on the research-area. The data, collected for this research was divided into 2 different data-groups: (i) primary-data, that was collected by the author & (ii) secondary-data, that was collected by various secondary-sources and data gathering-process (**Table 13**) (**Figure 26**: Steps 2, 3, 4). Collected by the author, the primary-data for exploring the location of the CB, Keele University (i.e., for understanding building's orientation, type) included the screengrabs of google-earth maps & photographs of the interior, exteriors of the CB.

In order to decide the system-efficiency and capacity of the selected GBTs, first the detailed location-exploration of the CB & Keele was conducted. The existing secondary-data about the CB's building-specifications and yearly energy-usage was collected from the Keele Estate Team as shown in (**Table 13**). Clean-energy generation directly depends on the climate-conditions. Therefore, the compiled secondary-data and its annual average for the climate-specifications of Keele were collected from the UK Met Office, global climate atlases for deciding the sizes of the selected-GBTs (i.e., RETs).

Addressing the objectives-2, 3, the existing secondary-data was reviewed for exploring the state-of-the-art of the selected GBTs'-field (i.e., solar and wind power). Second, the compiled and derived secondary-data about the detailed system-specifications for the selected GBT-types, models as well as the water-usage of large-buildings were explored by document-review in order to lead the criteria-analysis. These data were collected from multiple documents of various secondary data-resources (**Table 13**) to finally analyse the NZE-status of the CB through data-analysis, explained later in this section. Document reviewing can also be involved in qualitative-research but with that case, it chiefly involves the qualitative-data. Here, it involved quantitative-data & data-collection methods. The data-collection was conducted at various points of time as the research moved forward, involving multiple data collection-resources.

Based on the set objective and collected-data, it can be hypothesized that “all retrofitted/installed GBTs for the CB's theoretical transformation into a NZEB will generate clean-energy that equals to or exceeds the CB's annual energy-demand”.

3.3 Data Analysis (DA)

The major research-aim of this case-study incorporated the conceptual retrofitting of GBTs and a passive design measure to the existing-CB. The objectives, set for fulfilling this aim, identified, adopted methods for collecting the sets of real-world data, that could be measured or quantified to establish the research-findings. This convention is usually linked to the data that represents reality (i.e., called generalized static-data) without the influence of human-bias

or interpretation. Thus, the presented research involved facts and/or fact-based assumptions, leading to the research-philosophy of ‘*positivism*’. Majority of the data-collection methods, linked to this research-philosophy incorporates ‘quantitative data-collection and analysis methods’ (Blaikie, 2003).

The data-collection methods indicated an exploratory-nature, leading to a bottom-up approach of analysing-data (i.e., EDA) to check the feasibility of the included ZEB-measures and establish findings. The collected data was analysed, separately for each sample (i.e., GBT) as mentioned in (Fig. 26: step 5). The proposed-research incorporated two specific GBTs (i.e., solar-technologies, wind-technology) and one passive design measure (i.e., green-facades). The variables, affecting the retrofitted solar-technologies (i.e., rooftop solar-PVs & solar-PV trees) differed from the variables, affecting the wind-technology (VAWTs) throughout the data-analysis process. In other words, solar-energy generation depends, chiefly on solar-variables like solar irradiation, whereas, the wind-energy generation depends on wind-speed and air-density. Usually, the variables within a specific sample remain similar throughout the DA (Thompson, 2009). However, there is no strong-correlation between the variables of 2 different GBTs (e.g. solar-energy output is not strongly affected by wind-variables), thus, the proposed research did not adopt the inferential-correlation data analysis-approach.

Within the EDA, the proposed case-study undertook a ‘descriptive data analysis (DDA)-approach’, based on descriptive-statistics. The DDA statistical-method of mean (M or \bar{X}) or average was adopted to extract the average-data from annual data-sets of the variables (Thompson, 2009) (Fig. 28). However, the universal mathematical formulas and specific statistical-data for the case-study location were adopted from document reviewing in order to analyse the energy-outputs from selected GBT-retrofits. This was because the major aim of this case-study was to analyse the viability of the CB’s transformation into a NZEB through clean energy-generation by the GBTs.

Figure 28. Flowchart of the Data Analysis Methods for the Proposed Research

Lastly, the gathered location as well as building-specification secondary-data was adopted for designing the passive-design feature of the CB’s facades.

3.3.1.GBTs

Previous studies, conducted to examine the drivers of the GBTs wider adaptation included the increased resource, environment and energy performance & reduced long-term life-cycle costs of the buildings. Besides green and NZE-buildings develop a good professional reputation as they establish a triangular-relationship among the three-aspects of sustainable-development: society, ecology/environment and economy within the building (Darko et al., 2017). As, hypothesized earlier, the GBTs, retrofitted on the CB would generate clean-energy to compensate the building's yearly energy-demand after its transformation into a NZEB.

3.3.1.1. Solar-Energy Generation: Solar-PVs

For the proposed case-study of the CB, the majority of energy-generation would be carried out by the solar-PVs because the CB is one of the largest buildings at Keele with larger rooftop/terrace-area and is oriented towards South to slight-SE. The optimal solar-PV directions for the UK in northern-hemisphere are South, South-West & South-East, respectively with the tilt-angle of 35° from the horizon (Ingrams, 2022). Solar azimuth-angle is also considered for PV-orientation, that is “*an angle between the North and the sun with PV-panels on the local-horizon*”. Here, the local-horizon refers to the horizontal-plan on which the solar-PVs are installed/retrofitted. Azimuth for all solar-PVs facing S-SE in northern-hemisphere is generally considered 160° - 180° (Jacobson and Jadhav, 2018; Sena, 2021). For the proposed case-study, all solar-PVs, would be retrofitted at the tilt of 35° -angle, facing S to slight-SE, where the azimuth is assumed 180° . The solar-PVs, retrofitted on and nearby (i.e., on-site) the CB would receive moderate to high solar-irradiation, annually with the output of ~ 92 to 100% with the mentioned PV-orientation (Charles, 2019) (see appendix [B]-9).

Interestingly, a recent study on a utility-scale Hadley solar-farm with south-facing PVs in the UK revealed that the strong southerly-winds may affect the solar energy-generation. The generation can be increased at around ± 3.5 m/s wind-speed (Vasel and Iakovidis, 2017), however, the wind-directions for an entire year can never be constant (Turgeon and Morse, 2022). Hence, this variable for the proposed case-study has not been taken into consideration for the power-output calculations.

Note: These parameters were applied to both solar-PVs in this case-study.

(I) Rooftop/Terrace Mounted Solar-PVs:

Theoretically, the commercial M-series SunPower solar-PVs (**Figure 29**) with the panel-efficiency of 22.3% were retrofitted for the rooftop-installation in this project. A total of 82 solar-PVs (54 & 26 PVs on CBA & CBC-rooftop/terraces, respectively) were installed with inverters (i.e., for DC to AC transformation) to generate solar-power for the building-operations and import energy to the CB & the grid. These PV-modules were chosen because of their composition with one of the high-efficiency solar-cells that can provide good energy-output.

Figure 29. A Diagram of the Rooftop-Retrofitted PVs: SunPower Maxeon Commercial M-Series (Edited after SunPower, No Date) (**Note:** PV-Specifications, See Appendix [A]-11)

Figure 30. A Screenshot of the Global Solar Atlas, Showing the Annual Average Global Horizontal Irradiation Data in kWh/m² for Keele, UK (PVOUT map, 2022)

The data for average annual sunshine-hours from 1990-2020 was collected from the Met Office-website for Keele for a reference, which indicated a total of 4 annual average peak-hours/day (see, Appendix [A]-12). However, the global solar atlas was utilized for directly collecting the accurate annual average solar irradiation data for Keele as mentioned in (**Figure 30**).

Performance-ratio showcases the overall losses through PV at a specific-location, as shown below & usually ranges from 0.5 to 0.9%. PR, in simpler terms, relates to the quality of the system (i.e., the quality-factor), independent of the location but indicates the relation between the conceptual and practical solar-PV output (Steenburg, 2021). “The closer the PR-value to 100% for the PV-system, the more efficient the respective PV-system’s operation”, however, in real-world, 100% operating-efficiency is impossible to achieve. To mathematically calculate the PR in real world, metre readings of the PVs are monitored over a prolonged-period (SMA Solar Technology AG, No Date). However, for the proposed-research the overall-PR was considered 0.75%, including the losses mentioned: dust-losses (1-2%); inverter-losses (4-

10%); DC & AC cables –losses (1-3%); temperature-losses (5 to 20%); 0% shading for the selected location due to its clear neighbourhood, ~10-12m of building-height & weak radiation-losses (3-7%). An ‘online solar-energy output software’ was utilized to calculate the solar-output for the CB, that utilized the given formula (Photovoltaic Software, 2022).

Note: PR-value is considered on the basis of the azimuth and PVs’ orientation-tilt angles, that were 180° and 35°, respectively for the optimal energy-output.

Table 14. Specifications of the Rooftop/Terrace-Retrofitted SunPower Maxeon Commercial M-Series Solar PVs on the CB (Marszal et al., 2011; Photovoltaic Software, 2022; PVOUT map, 2022) (**Note:** See **Fig.s 29, 30**; For PV-Module Specification, See Appendix [A]-11)

Power (P)	475 watt or 0.475 kw
Panel Efficiency (r) (in %)	22.3%
Total Area of a Single PV-Panel or PV-Module (A) (in m ²)	2.126 m ²
Direction of the PVs	South to South-East (See Appendix [C]-2)
Solar Panel Tilt or Tilting-Angle (°)	35°
Azimuth Angle (°)	180°
Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (PR) (in %)	0.75 %
Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted PV (n kWh/m ² annual) (Excluding the Shading) (H)	954.5 kWh/m ²

The mathematical-formula for analysing annual solar-energy generation by solar-PVs (Source: Photovoltaic Software, 2022; Marszal et al., 2011)

$$E = A * r * H * PR$$

Where,

E = Energy (kWh)

A = Total Area of a Solar PV-Panel or PV-Module (m²)

r = Solar-Panel or Module Efficiency (%)

H = Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted Solar PV (Excluding the Shading) (kWh/m²)

PR = Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (%)

(II) Solar-PV Trees:

The solar-trees comprise a trunk, branched PV-leaves, made with high-efficiency solar-PVs to harness clean-energy. Leaves with perovskite, mono or poly-crystalline solar-cells can harness good amount of solar-energy/year, depending on the climate-type. The branched metal-trunk comprise internal-space for storage-batteries, battery-charger, cables, inverter & ACS. The exterior usually comprises metallic-base and external USB-plugging for direct mechanical-use. The eight 18'-0" tall lift-type solar PV-trees were chosen for retrofitting nearby the CB for on-site generation as shown in (Fig. 31). The PV-orientation is considered similar as the roof-top PVs with the tilt of 35° & azimuth of 180° for optimal-output with the S-facing direction. The trees comprised 2-PV leaves, each with 6 commercial M-series SunPower solar-PVs (Fig. 29).

Figure 31. Diagram of the Retrofitted Solar-PV Tree (Edited after SunPower, No Date)
(Note: For PV Specifications, See Appendix [A]-13)

Continued...

Table 15. Specifications of the Installed Lift Solar-PV Trees (Edited After Solar Trees, No Date; Photovoltaic Software, 2022; PVOUT map, 2022) (See, **Fig.s 30, 31**; For System Specifications, See Appendix [A]-13)

Power (P)	475 watt or 0.475 kw
Panel Efficiency (r) (in %)	22.3%
Total Area of 2 Leaves with 12 PVs (A) (in m ²)	12.7 m ²
Direction of the PVs	South (See Appendix [C]-2)
Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (PR) (in %)	0.75 %
Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted PV (n kWh/m ² annual) (Excluding the Shading) (H)	954.5 kWh/m ²

With the use of same online solar-energy output calculating-software, the energy-output was calculated, considering the following formula, specifications (**Table 15**).

The mathematical-formula for analysing annual solar-energy generation by solar-PV trees (Source: Photovoltaic Software, 2022; Marszal et al., 2011)

$$E = A * r * H * PR$$

Where,

E = Energy (kWh)

A = Total Area of a Solar PV-Panel or PV-Module (m²)

r = Solar-Panel or Module Efficiency (%)

H = Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted Solar PV (Excluding the Shading) (kWh/m²)

PR = Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (%)

Note: Solar PV trees are S-facing and the rooftop/terrace mount PVs are slightly S-E (i.e., very close to the direct-South), thus, the orientation and angle-specifications for both the PV-installations are considered similar.

3.3.1.2. Wind-Energy Generation: Helical-VAWT

A total of 16 helix or helical-spiral type VAWT were theoretically retrofitted on the existing-CBA's high-terrace (Elevation of level-3: ~12m) for on-site microgeneration. Here, each system with the power of 6500 W comprises 2 turbine-blades and 0.525 m of turbine-diameter. With the turbine-efficiency of 30%, these VAWTs can operate from 2 m/s of wind-speed & the temperature-range of -25°C to about +45°C. Moreover, Keele has a diverse range of monthly wind-speeds/year, thus, the accurate mean wind-speed was taken into consideration from the global wind-atlas (**Fig. 33**) to calculate the wind-energy output. Along with that, the air-density of the UK (i.e., for Keele) was adopted as 1.225 kg/m³ as it generally remains similar across the UK, considering the air-pressure, moisture and air-temperature (Met Office,

No Date). These VAWTs are viable, cost-efficient and environmentally low-impact wind-turbines with good system-adaptability for a diverse range wind-speed. Additionally, they can produce wind-energy with winds from any direction with low to minimal noise-pollution (Kumar et al., 2018). This along with the high-efficiency of the chosen VAWT-system would make the helical VAWTs a suitable retrofit choice for the CB.

Figure 32. The Diagram of the Retrofitted Helix or Helical Spiral Type VAWT (Amazon, 2022) (Note: See, Appendix [A]-14 for System Specifications)

Figure 33. A Screenshot of Global Wind Atlas, Showing the Wind Data of Keele, UK (GBA, 2021)

Table 16. Specifications of the Retrofitted Helical-VAWTs on the CB (Amazon, 2022; Reza et al., 2015) (See, **Fig.s 32, 33**)

Model Type	Helix or Helical Spiral Type VAWT
Diameter (D) (in m)	0.525 m
Radius (r) (in m)	0.26 m
Sweeping Area (A) (in m ²)	0.21 m ²
Air Density (ρ) (in kg/m ³)	1.225 kg/m ³
Wind Speed (V) (m/s)	8.9 m/s
Turbine Efficiency (ηT) (in %)	30% or 0.3
Generator Efficiency (ηG) (in %)	90% or 0.9
Power or Generation (P) (in kWh/Annual)	0.12 kWh
Total Working Hours per Day (Annually Assumed for the Selected Location)	20 Hours
Total Working Hours per Year (Annually Assumed for the Selected Location)	7300 Hours

Next, a mathematical-formula, specific to helical-VAWTs' wind-energy output was adopted for calculation.

The mathematical-formula for analysing annual wind-energy generation by the helical or helix HAWTs (**Table 16**) (Source: Reza et al., 2015)

$$P = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \rho A V^3 \eta T \eta G}{1000}$$

Where,

P = Power (kWh)

ρ = Air Density (kg/m³)

A = Sweeping Area (m²)

V = Wind Speed (m/s)

ηT = Turbine Efficiency

ηG = Generator Efficiency

3.3.2. VGS: Green-Facades

The VGSs are natural, aesthetically-appealing, cost-efficient, environmentally rewarding and less time-consuming passive-techniques for building's external-insulation and natural-cooling. The green-roof is also an alternative-development for the energy-saving buildings but the living-walls/facades are usually 5-20% more efficient than the green-roofs (Perez et al., 2014), depending on the building-size. The proposed case-study involved the retrofitting of rooftop/terrace-based GBTs. Therefore, the research incorporated the conceptual-development of 'indirect green-facades' (**Fig. 34-(a)**:-indirect) of the central-building of the CB, 'the CBA'. It would improve the building's external-outlook, microclimate & occupant's health in the future after its full-development. As the CBA has symmetrically rectangular-structure, it was

selected for the VGS-development. The data of the ground-cover, height of the walls & facades of the CBA are unavailable, thus, the study was conducted considering the assumption based-data, taken from the google-earth imagery & document-review.

Figure 34. Types of Vertical Greenery Systems: (a) Green-Facades, (b) Vertical Green Living Walls (Bustami et al., 2018)

- **Materials & Development-Method**

The selected plant-materials included 2 species-varieties of *Hedera helix*: (i) Pittsburgh-Green or English Ivy & (ii) Goldchild. These Ivy-varieties represent lush-green foliage and itched-yellow & green-leaves, respectively. It would give the facades a balanced-coloured outlook as green and yellow are complementary-colours (Nuwer, 2012). Four sides of the building-‘CBA’ represents different heights of walls and facades (Fig. 35). Thus, the dimensions/sizes of the required materials varied for the green-façade systems for the CBA. Metallic-strings, as per the height of the external-walls and respective-facades of the CBA (Table 17), were retrofitted by metal-screws (i.e., 2 per each string) for the vertical expansion of the selected foliage to conceptually create the direct green-façade. (Table 21).

Figure 35. Directions of the Sides of the CBA, Considered for the Development of Green-Facades (Edited after Google Earth, No Date. f)

Table 17. A Table Showing the Number and Height of Available Facades of the External-Walls of the CBA (**Note:** See **Fig. 35** for the Building-Orientation)

Orientation or Direction of the Wall	Approximate Height of the Wall & Façade (m)	No. of Vertical-Columns (i.e., Facades), Available for the VGS Development on the Wall
Slight North-East	~12m	25
Slight North-West	~12m & ~7m, respectively	2 & 9, respectively
South-West	~5m	11 (Excluding the Ground-Level)
South-East	~12m	1 (Excluding the Ground-Level)
(Note: Café & Kitchen-Areas or Roofed-Areas in the Fig. 35 are Excluded)		

The metal-strings were attached to the facades of the CBA (see, **Table 21**), using the screws near the bottom and top to create ‘double-skinned green-facades’. The double-skin provided plants with an air-chamber of around 20cm between the strings & the façade in order to give foliage the required expansion-space. The mentioned varieties of *Hedera helix* were planted, alternatively in the soil, where the ground was available & in the planters, where the ground was not available (**Table 21**) (Coma et al., 2017). *Hedera helix* or Ivy-climber was selected as it is a fast-growing woody, evergreen plant, highly adoptable to the UK-weather. These varieties comprise dense-foliage (each leaf: 2-4-inch-long), thus, providing a good level of insulation and shading to the covered-areas. Moreover, a recent study indicated that the Ivy-species act as natural-coolants reduce the buildings’ temperature to at least 1°C in summer. Once fully developed, the Ivy-façade would lower the CBA’s temperature to ~3-5°C in the hot summer-months (RHS, 2022).

3.3.3. Water Demand Profile

The second part of the proposed-research aimed to analyse the estimation-based annual water-demand profile of the CB through document-review as shown in (**Figure 26**: Steps 6). Being one of the largest structures, the CB would have moderately high-water usage as it houses a total of 419 internal-spaces with 34 total spaces with major water-use (19 lavatories, 15 catering-spaces) (**Table 22**).

The (**Table 22**) indicates an assumed optimal-water use of the entire CB. The compiled 2^o-data were directly collected, modified and adopted from the reports on the large-buildings by (EIA, 2012), through reviewing for making estimations of the annual water-usage of the CB. This was because, the annual water-usage of the CB has not been metred, recorded by the university. The chosen probability sampling-approach allowed this research to adopt random-selection of data from the (EIA, 2012)-report. Here, the DDA approach was used, indirectly. In other words, the annual compiled 2^o-data of the water-use for large-buildings was adopted by representative-selection from the water-usage data-sets of various types of large-buildings. The adopted and/or modified data was multiplied with the ‘total number of internal-spaces, using water’ & ‘overall water-leak estimates’ to analyse the ‘annual water-demand profile’ of the CB. These estimations of annual-water use of a mixed-use building like the CB would provide a reference and an overall idea about the impact of large-buildings’ water-profile on the university’s water-demand. A few previous-studies consist systematic statistical-methods for analysing the water-use of residential/non-residential buildings, however, the adaptation of these statistics require the sets of recorded metre-readings or utility billing-data of the water-usage (Morales, et al., 2009).

Overall, the quantitative methodological-approach with EDA in the presented case-study of the CB provided a range of data-collection (**Figure 27**) & data-analysis methods (**Figure 28**) to address the set objectives. To attain the (**Figure 26**: Steps 5, 6), the next chapter will concisely establish the main findings of the proposed-research.

4. Results

With the case study-based research approach, the proposed research aimed to investigate the viability of the transformation of the CB at Keele University into a functional-NZEB by theoretically or conceptually retrofitting various GBTs (**Table 12**) and introducing a passive design aspect to produce clean-energy, that equals to the CB's annual energy-demand profile. Secondly, it aimed to analyse the estimation-based yearly water-demand profile of the CB by reviewing previous literature. With a quantitative methodological-approach, the proposed-research incorporated various data-collection and analysis methods, as described in the previous chapter. The first two objectives of the proposed case-study were addressed by collecting data and reviewing literature in the previous chapters.

To attain the third objective of the proposed-research, this chapter will provide a brief roadmap to understand the composition of the selected GBTs, passive design feature and CB's annual water-usage. It will analyse the mentioned features to calculate the overall clean-energy generation by the retrofitted-GBTs & synthesize the chief findings: (i) 'energy demand-supply profile' & (ii) 'water demand-profile' of the CB.

4.1. GBTs

The proposed case-study incorporated two solar-energy technologies (rooftop/terrace mount solar-PVs & PV-trees) & wind-energy technology (helical-HAWTs) (**Table 12**) for clean energy-generation.

4.1.1. Solar-Energy Generation: Solar-PVs

As pre-described in 'methodology', the optimal-directions for solar-power generation through the solar-PVs in the UK is South, S-W & S-E, respectively, with a 35° of tilt-angle from the horizon (Ingrams, 2022; Charles, 2019). The CB's solar-PV technologies were retrofitted towards S-SE with the tilt of 35°, azimuth of 180° & the overall PR (i.e., overall system-losses) of 0.75%, as mentioned earlier (Steenburg, 2021). The PR-value was considered on the basis of the azimuth, PVs'-tilt angle for the optimal energy-output. As mentioned earlier, for the reference, the mean annual sunshine-hours for Keele from 1990-2020 were studied from the (**Fig. 36**) (Met Office, No Date), that indicated ~4 peak hours/day for solar-irradiation. However, the accurate mean or average annual solar irradiation for Keele (i.e., 954.5 kWh/m²) was directly adopted by the global solar atlas (**Fig. 30**).

Figure 36. A Reference Graph, Showing Symmetrical Distribution of Data of the Average Annual Sunshine-Hours for Keele, UK (Redrawn after Met Office, No Date) (**Note:** See Appendix [A]-12)

(I) Rooftop/Terrace Mounted Solar-PVs:

Considering the factors mentioned, a total of 82 SunPower Maxeon solar-PVs of 475 watts of power were retrofitted on the rooftop/terrace of the CB for solar-power generation. An online-software with the given formula was used for the calculation of solar-energy generation, considering the specifications listed in (**Table 18**) (Photovoltaic Software, 2022).

Table 18. A Table Showing the Energy-Generation Calculations of Rooftop/Terrace-Retrofitted SunPower Maxeon Commercial M-Series Solar-PVs (Marszal et al., 2011; Photovoltaic Software, 2022; PVOUT map, 2022) (**Note:** See **Figs 29, 30**; For PV-Module Specification, See Appendix [A]-11)

Power (P)	475 watt or 0.475 kw
Panel Efficiency (η) (in %)	22.3%
Total Area of a Single PV-Panel or PV-Module (A) (in m^2)	2.126 m^2
Direction of the PVs	South to South-East (See Appendix [C]-2)
Solar Panel Tilt or Tilting-Angle ($^\circ$)	35 $^\circ$
Azimuth Angle ($^\circ$)	180 $^\circ$
Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (PR) (in %)	0.75 %
Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted PV (n kWh/ m^2 annual) (Excluding the Shading) (H)	954.5 kWh/ m^2
Energy Output of a Single PV-Module (E) (in kWh)	354 kWh/Year
Energy Output for 82 Solar PVs, Facing the S to SE	29,028 kWh/Year

Calculation Box. 1 Analysis of the Annual Solar-Energy Generation by Solar-PV Modules as Shown in (**Table 18**) (Source: Photovoltaic Software, 2022; Marszal et al., 2011)

$$E = A * r * H * PR$$

Where,

E = Energy (kWh)

A = Total Area of a Solar PV-Panel or PV-Module (m²)

r = Solar-Panel or Module Efficiency (%)

H = Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted Solar PV (Excluding the Shading) (kWh/m²)

PR = Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (%)

Therefore,

$$E = 2.126 * 22.3 * 954.5 * 0.75$$

$$E = 354 \text{ kWh/Year}$$

$$\text{Total 82 Solar-PVs} * 354 \text{ kWh/Year} = 29,028 \text{ kWh/Year}$$

- **The key finding of the solar-energy output by a total of 82 high-efficiency rooftop/terrace solar-PVs, mounted on the CB, Keele for on-site generation indicated the energy-output of 29,028 kWh/Year, considering the factors mentioned above.**

(II) Solar-PV Trees:

Considering the factors mentioned, a total of 8 S-facing lift solar-PV trees, made of PVs with 475 watts of power were retrofitted nearby the CB for solar-power generation. An online-software with the given formula was used for the calculation of solar-energy generation, considering the specifications listed in (**Table 19**) (Photovoltaic Software, 2022).

Table 19 (continued). A Table Showing the Energy-Generation Calculations of Retrofitted Lift Solar-PV Trees (Edited After Solar Trees, No Date; Photovoltaic Software, 2022; PVOUT map, 2022) (**Note:** See, **Fig.s 30, 31**; For PV-Module Specification, See Appendix [A]-13)

PV-Power (P)	475 watt or 0.475 kw
Panel Efficiency (r) (in %)	22.3%
Total Area of 2 Leaves with 12 PVs (A) (in m ²)	12.7 m ²
Direction of the PVs	South (See Appendix [C]-2)
Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (PR) (in %)	0.75 %
Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted PV (n kWh/m ² annual) (Excluding the Shading) (H)	954.5 kWh/m ²
Energy of a Single PV-Tree System (E) (in kWh)	2026 kWh/Year

Energy Output 8 PV-Tree System (E) (in kWh)	16,208 kWh/Year
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Calculation Box. 2 Analysis of the Annual Solar-Energy Generation by Solar-PV Trees as Shown in (Table 19) (Source: Photovoltaic Software, 2022; Marszal et al., 2011)

$E = A * r * H * PR$
Where,
E = Energy (kWh)
A = Total Area of a Solar PV-Panel or PV-Module (m²)
r = Solar-Panel or Module Efficiency (%)
H = Annual Average Solar Radiation on the Tilted Solar PV (Excluding the Shading) (kWh/m²)
PR = Performance Ratio, Coefficient of Losses (%)

Therefore,
 $E = 12.7 * 22.3 * 954.5 * 0.75$
E = 2026 kWh/Year

Total 8 PV-Tree System * 2026 kWh/Year = 16,208 kWh/Year

- **The key finding of the solar-energy output by a total of 8 lift-type solar-PV trees, mounted nearby the CB, Keele for on-site generation indicated the energy-output of 16,208 kWh/Year, considering the factors mentioned above.**

4.1.2. Wind-Energy Generation: Helical-VAWT

Keele indicates diverse wind-speeds per month in the given year (for a reference, see Fig. 37). Thus, the accurate yearly mean wind-speed was taken into consideration from the global wind-atlas (Fig. 33) to calculate the wind-energy output of the retrofitted VAWTs for the CB. The UK air-density, as pre-described in methodology, was adopted as 1.225 kg/m³ for the proposed case-study of the CB at Keele (Met Office, No Date).

continued...

Figure 37. A Reference Graph, Showing the Data of Monthly Average Wind Speed for Keele & Newcastle-under-Lyme, UK (Redrawn after Met Office, No Date) (**Note:** See Appendix [A]-12)

For the proposed-research, each VAWT-system with the power of 6500 W comprised 2 turbine-blades, 0.525 m of turbine-diameter and 0.21 m² of sweeping-area. With the 30% of turbine-efficiency the retrofitted-VAWTs can operate from the wind-speed of 2 m/s & temperature-range of -25°C to around +45°C. The specific data-analysis of the helical-VAWTs' wind-energy output was carried out by a mathematical-formula, mentioned below. As pre-described in methodology, a 16 helical VAWTs were retrofitted on the terraces of the CB for on-site microgeneration.

Table 20. A Table Showing the Energy-Generation Calculations of Retrofitted Helical-VAWT (Amazon, 2022; Reza et al., 2015) (**Note:** **Fig.s 32, 33;** See Appendix [A]-14 for System Specifications)

Model Type	Helix or Helical Spiral Type VAWT
Diameter (D) (in m)	0.525 m
Radius (r) (in m)	0.26 m
Sweeping Area (A) (in m ²)	0.21 m ²
Air Density (ρ) (in kg/m ³)	1.225 kg/m ³
Wind Speed (V) (m/s)	8.9 m/s
Turbine Efficiency (ηT) (in %)	30% or 0.3
Generator Efficiency (ηG) (in %)	90% or 0.9
Power or Generation (P) (in kWh/Annual)	0.12 kWh
Total Working Hours per Day (Annually Assumed for the Selected Location)	20 Hours
Total Working Hours per Year (Annually Assumed for the Selected Location)	7300 Hours
Generation by Single VAWT (P) (in kWh/Annual)	219 kWh/Year
Total Generation by 16 VAWTs	3504 kWh/Year

Calculation Box. 3 Analysis of the Annual Wind-Energy Generation by VAWTs as Shown in (Table 20) (Source: Reza et al., 2015)

$$P = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \rho AV^3 \eta T \eta G}{1000}$$

Where,

P = Power (kWh)

ρ = Air Density (kg/m³)

A = Sweeping Area (m²)

V = Wind Speed (m/s)

ηT = Turbine Efficiency

ηG = Generator Efficiency

Therefore,

$$A = \text{Sweeping Area (m}^2\text{)} = \pi * (r)^2 = 3.12 * (0.26)^2 = 0.21 \text{ m}^2 \text{ ___(i)}$$

$$P = \frac{0.5 * 1.225 * 0.21 * 704.9 * 0.3 * 0.9}{1000} = 0.02448 \text{ kWh} = 0.03 \text{ kWh ___(ii)}$$

Therefore, a single VAWT with daily 20 working hours/day provides 0.03 kWh/day & a single VAWT with daily 7300 working hours/year provides 876 kWh/year

$$P = 219 \text{ kWh/Year ___(iii)}$$

$$\text{Total 16 Helical HAWT} * 219 \text{ kWh/Year} = 3504 \text{ kWh/Year ___(iv)}$$

- **The key finding of the wind-energy output by a total of 16 helical or helix-type VAWTs, mounted nearby the high terrace of CBA, the CB Keele for an on-site micro-generation indicated the wind-energy output of 3504 kWh/Year, considering the factors mentioned above.**

4.2. VGS: Green-Facades

As shown in (Figure 35, Table 17), the CBA was selected for the green-façade development as a part of passive design measure. As pre-described in methodology, four different sides of the CBA indicated difference in the heights of walls and respective facades.

The key findings (See, Table 21) for the green-facades development as a passive-design measure in the case-study of CB (i.e., here CBA) indicated:

- The 25 facades of the N-E side with the heights of 12 m required a total of 50 metal-strings (i.e., 12 m long) for the vertical-growth of the foliage.
- The 2 large-facades of the N-W side with the heights of 12 m required total 6 metal-strings (i.e., 12 m long). Similarly, the 9 moderate-sized facades of the N-W side with the heights of 7 m required total 9 metal-strings (i.e., 7 m long) for the vertical-growth of Ivy-climbers. Here, the plants were cultivated in 9 different, ground-based planters due to the lack of soil near the 9-barrow facades.

- The 11 small-facades of the S-W side with the heights of 5 m required total 22 metal-strings (i.e., 5 m long) for the vertical-growth of Ivy-climbers.
- 1 long-facades of the S-E side of the CBA with the heights of 12 m required total 2 metal-strings (i.e., 12 m long) for the vertical-growth of Ivy-climbers. The plants were cultivated in 1 ground-based planter due to the lack of soil.
- The total materials required here, involved a total of 89 metallic-strings of 2 mm size for growing the foliage on the facades, 178 metal-screws (i.e., 2/each string) & 10 ground-based planters for 48 facades of the CBA (**Table 21**).

Table 21. A Table Showing the Number and Height of Metallic-Strings for the Available Facades of the External-Walls of the CBA (**Note:** See **Table 17, Figure 35** for the CBA-Orientation)

Orientation or Direction of the Wall	No. of Vertical Columns (i.e., Facades), Available for the VGS Development on the Wall	Length of the Vertical-Strings (m) (Note: Same as the respective Façade Height)	No. of Vertical Metallic-Strings	Remark	No. of Ground Pot/Planter for Planting the Climbers
Slight North-East	25	~12m	50	2 strings on each narrow façade (52 facades * 2 strings= 50 strings)	Planted directly in the ground
Slight North-West	2 & 9, respectively	~12m & ~7m, respectively	6 & 9, respectively	(3 Strings * 2 broad facades= 6 string) & (1 strings * 9 narrow façade= 9 strings)	Planted directly in the ground for board Facades; 9 ground-planters for narrow facades
South-West	11	~5m	22	2 strings on each narrow façade (11 facades * 2 strings= 22 strings)	Planted directly in the ground
South-East	1	~12m	2	2 strings on the long narrow façade (1 facades * 2 strings= 2 strings)	1 ground-planter for 1 narrow façade
Overall:	48	-	89 Strings		10 Pots

4.3. Water Demand Profile

Note, that the primary-data of the CB's annual water-usage has not been recorded by the university. The collected, modified & adopted- 2° data (EIA, 2012) for the CB is indicated in (Table 22) for each type or water-use in the large-buildings. The (Table 22) shows an assumption-based optimal yearly water-demand of the entire CB.

Table 22. Estimations, Showing the Optimal Water Usage of the CB per Year (Edited, Adopted after EIA, 2012)

➤ Water Use in Lavatory (Total 19)				
No. of Toilet	Water Use in Single-Flush (Litre)	No. of Flushes/Day	Water Use for Overall Flushes/Day (Litre)	Water Use for Overall Flushes/year (Litre) (Vacation Months, Holidays Included)
1	5	45	225	82,125
5 Toilets (per 1 Lavatory)	25 (5 per toilet)	225	1125	4,10,625
95 Toilets (19 Lavatories)	475 (5 per toilet)	4275	21,375	78,01,875
➤ Water-Leak & Dripping Water				
No. of Lavatory	Water Leak in Litres/Day	Water Leak in Litres/Year		
1	400	1,46,000		
19	7600	27,74,000		
➤ Catering Spaces (Including the Central Café & Kitchen) (Total 15)				
Catering Space	Water Use in Litres/Day	Water Use in Litres/Year		
Central Cafe	2727.65	995,593.25		
Catering-Spaces, Including Drinking water, Cooking, Cleaning & Sink Usage	20,819.76	7,599,212.4		
Overall Water Use in All Catering Spaces	23,547.41	8,594,805.65		
Overall Water Use o the CB = 19,170,680.65 litres/year				

The key findings (Table 22) on the CB’s optimal annual water-demand profile are estimated as:

- The estimated annual water-use in 19 lavatories (i.e., total 95 toilets) in the CB can approximately be 78,01,875 litres/year, with a total of 4275/day in an entire year.
- The estimated annual water-waste in all 19 lavatories by leaks & dripping-water in the CB can approximately be 27,74,000 litres/year, considering the water-waste of 400 litres/day.
- The estimated annual water-waste in all 15 catering-spaces (including the central café & kitchen) for the activities like cooking, cleaning & sink run-off, drinking can approximately be 8,594,805.65 litres/year.
- The estimated overall, optimal, annual water-use or water-demand of the CB can approximately be 19,170,680.65 litres/year.

4.4. Overall Findings

(Table 23 to 25) show the key findings of the annual clean energy-generation, green-façade development & the annual water demand or use profile of the CB at Keele University. The overall clean-energy generation by the retrofitted GBTs on and/or nearby the CB accounted for 48,740 kWh/year (Table 23), given the climatic-measures, mentioned above. The assumption-based overall optimal water-usage of the CB is estimated to be 19,170,680.65 litres/year (Table 25).

Table 23. Key Findings of the Clean-Energy Generation by the Retrofitted/Installed GBTs in the Proposed Case-Study

GBT	No. of Total Retrofits/Installations	Clean-Energy Generation (kWh/Year)
Rooftop/Terrace Mounted Solar-PVs	82	29,028
Solar-PV Trees	8	16,208
Wind-Energy Generation: Helical-VAWT	16	3504
Overall:	106	48,740

Table 24(continued). Key Findings of the Passive Design Aspect (i.e., Green-Façade Development) for the Proposed Case-Study

Orientation or Direction of the CBA Wall	No. of Vertical Columns/Facades of the CBA	No. of Vertical Metallic-Strings	No. of Ground Pot/Planter
Slight North-East	25	50	Ground-planted
Slight North-West	2 & 9, respectively	6 & 9, respectively	Ground-planted & 9 planters, respectively
South-West	11 (Excluding the Ground-Level)	22	Ground-planted
South-East	1 (Excluding the Ground-Level)	2	1 ground-planter

Overall:	48	178 metal-screws (i.e., 2/each string	10 Planter
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Table 25. Key Findings of the Optimal Annual Water Demand or Usage of the CB

Internal Spaces of the CB	No. of Internal Spaces of the CB	Optimal Water Use/Year (Litres/Year)
Lavatory	19	78,01,875
Catering Spaces (Including the Central Café & Kitchen)	15	8,594,805.65
Water-Leak & Dripping Water	-	27,74,000
Overall:	34	19,170,680.65

5. Discussion

The proposed-research with the case study-based research-approach, aimed to investigate the viability of the transformation of the CB into a functional-NZEB through conceptually or theoretically retrofitting different GBTs & introducing a passive design aspect (**Table 12**) to produce clean-energy, that equals to the CB's yearly energy-demand profile. Second, it aimed to analyse the estimation-based annual water-demand profile of the CB by reviewing previous literature.

The analysed data indicate that a total of 82 'rooftop/terrace mounted solar-PVs' & '8 lift-type solar-PV trees' generate 29,028 & 16,208 kWh/year of solar-energy (E), respectively. Similarly, it also indicates that the 16 helical VAWTs generate 3504 kWh of the wind-energy (P), annually. The analysed data suggests that the overall clean-energy, produced by the retrofitted/installed GBTs is 48,740 kWh/year (**Table 23**). The assumption-based optimal water-use of the CB is estimated to be 19,170,680.65 litres/year (**Table 25**).

5.1. Energy Demand-Supply Profile of the CB

In line with the hypothesis, the clean-energy generation (i.e., 48,740 kWh/year) by theoretically retrofitted/installed GBTs exceeds the CB's annual energy usage or demand, which accounts for 46,917 kWh/year (Keele Estate Team). Theoretically, this indicates that the GBTs generate 1823 kWh of extra energy to export to the main-grid, annually. In other words, the results suggest that the clean-energy, generated on-site is more than the imported or delivered-energy on the annual basis (**Fig.16**) in the proposed case-study. By definition, "*the NZEB's annual net I^o-energy is lesser than or equal to zero across the building's-boundary*" (Lin and Chen, 2022), which establishes the energy-balance, required for achieving the 'net zero energy'-status as shown in (**Fig. 16**). Therefore,

Net Primary Energy of the NZEB = Total Imported Energy – Total Exported Energy ≤ 0
(Source: Lin and Chen, 2022; Cao et al., 2016)

Hence, the findings indicate, address & fulfil the objective-3 and major aim of the proposed-research of analysing the CB's annual 'energy demand-supply profile' as well as theoretically achieve the NZE-status as shown in (**Fig. 26**, Setp-5).

5.1.1. The GBTs

As mentioned earlier, the S-E facing rooftop/terrace mount solar-PVs receive an average solar-radiation (H) of 954.5 kWh/m²/year, considering the tilt-angle of 35°, azimuth of 180°. With the given PV-orientation, the PVs receive moderately-high solar-radiation (Charles, 2019). Therefore, here, the analysed solar-power yield (i.e., 29,028 kWh/year) is considered 'moderately-high' (between 92 to 96%). However, the same solar-PV modules with the given orientation and South-facing direction can provide higher annual yields (i.e., 96-100%) because of the higher exposure of light (Charles, 2019; Ingrams, 2022) for the given location. The CB has a possibility of mounting South-facing PVs, however, the building is oriented towards slight S-E direction. This can 'non-constructively affect: (i) the number of rooftop-mount solar-PVs, (ii) the total available area for mounting the solar-PVs, ultimately leading to the reduced solar-yield'. Second, as the data shows, the solar-energy output by a total of 8 solar-PV trees is 16,208 kWh/year, that is considered 'high to optimal' (i.e., 96-100%) due to the S-facing

direction of the PV-leaves. Overall, it can be interpreted that the annual solar-energy yield by the retrofitted/installed solar-GBTs is moderate to high (92-100%), in the given climatic and system conditions.

The rooftop/terrace retrofitted solar-PVs are considered as BAPVs with a high up-front installation-cost. However, the BAPV is the most suitable, easily available and installable retrofit-option with the long-term cost-benefits in the case of the CB (Kumar et al., 2019; Wu and Skye, 2021) as the CB has large rooftop and/or terrace-area. The retrofitted solar-PVs consist Maxeon Gen 6-solar cells, designed to maximally converse the low-light exposure during cloudy-days (SunPower, No Date). This suggests that the retrofitted systems will provide the overall financial-return in the shorter period of time.

Finally, retrofitted on the terraces of the CBA, a total of 16 helical-VAWTs generate 3504 kWh/year of wind-energy (P), considering the annual average wind-speed (V) of 8.9 m/s along with the specifications, shown in (Table 20). Although, Keele has a suitable range of annual mean V , the annual-output of these wind-turbines is significantly lower than the expected output. This is because of the smaller sweeping-area (A) of retrofitted-VAWTs. The higher the rotor swept-area, the higher the annual wind-energy production (Bortolotti et al., 2019). However, the low noise-pollution, system-vibration and remarkably eliminated visual-disturbance by the retrofitted-VAWTs (Reza, et al., 2015) are three significant factors for the on-site wind-microgeneration in the proposed case-study. This is because the chief use of the CB is related to academic-activities. On the basis of the results, it can be interpreted that the VAWTs are suitable for onsite-microgeneration but for higher annual-yield, the selection-criteria of the VAWTs should consider the blade-size, turbine-diameter, the rotor swept-area and the number of turbines, depending on the building-size. Considering the annual mean wind-speed of Keele, the energy-yield can practically be higher than represented in the proposed-research with larger VAWT-systems. In this case, the increase in the annual mean wind-speed will increase the annual operating/working-hours of the retrofitted turbines, producing more wind-energy in the given year. This indicates the correlation or direct relation between the annual mean wind-speed and turbine reliability (Tavner et al., 2006).

In theory, the generated clean-energy fulfils the CB's annual energy-demand and cuts its dependency on the conventional-resources, which aligns with Keele University's pledge of carbon-neutrality & the UK government's NZ-pledge & the NZEB-approach of "*net zero production of CO₂ from every type of energy-use in the house/building, in the given the year*" (Keele University, No Date. m; Omrany et al., 2022). In practice, it may not be possible to achieve and maintain the NZE-status for each given year throughout the CB's lifespan because of the two chief reasons: (i) the renewable-energy technologies directly rely on the local-climates, which can fluctuate significantly in the given year and affect the annual energy-generation by the retrofitted GBTs, (ii) the retrofitting of GBTs on a pre-existing building does not consider the emissions, released by the CB before achieving the NZEB-status (Jain and Rawal, 2022). However, practically, the NZEBs may also generate more energy than estimated if it has suitable weather-conditions, throughout the year.

Addressing the final objective 4, the extra generated-energy (i.e., 1823 kWh/year) from the CB will be exported to the main-grid, affecting the university's overall energy-demand profile and sustainability outlook. As a large, mixed-used building, the energy-independent CB will significantly affect the university's energy-outlook by not relying on the university for

electricity. The natural passive-design aspect of the green-facades will improve and beautify the CBA's external aesthetic-outlook through the patches of two different varieties of the Ivy. The Ivy-greenery will cause visual-stimuli, psychological-comfort to the building users/occupants & improve the building's air-quality (Safikhani et al., 2014). A heavy bulk of previous studies have indicated that the greenery decreases psychological-anxiety and physiological-stress by suppressing sympathetic nervous system (SNS) activities, releasing cortisol and maintaining heart rate variability (Roe et al., 2013; Cole, 2020; Chan et al., 2021). The VGSs of the CBA will significantly improve the overall working ability, well-being of Keele community by causing health benefits. Additionally, the large-rural and biologically diverse Keele campus houses ~1500 species. (Keele University, No Date. I). The green-facades of the CBA, after its complete-development will attract insects, birds and small vertebrates, supporting the vernacular ecosystem at Keele. Once flourished completely, the Ivy-foliage would be able to reduce the ambient- temperature of the CBA's external-walls by approximately 3-5°C (RHS, 2022), provide external-insulation and saving energy in the cooling % heating of the CBA. However, it is not calculated at this stage in the proposed-research for the CBA due to the lack of data/metered-readings, recorded by temperature monitoring-device.

5.2. Water Demand Profile of the CB

To address the objective-3 and the second-aim (see, **Fig. 26**, Setp-6) of analysing the water-use or demand profile of the CB, the (**Table 22**) represents the estimated water usage of the CB (i.e., 19,170,680.65 litres/year). Estimating a total of 4275 of flushes with 5 litres, the CB uses 21,375 & 78,01,875 litres of water per day and year in total 19 lavatories, respectively. Estimating the dripping-water of 7600 litres/day in all 19 lavatories, indicates the 27,74,000 litres/year of water-waste. Although assumption-based, these obtained results indicate the CB's high water-consumption/year. Similarly, 8,594,805.65 litres/year suggests a regularly high water-usage in all 15 catering, café-spaces at the CB.

This is because being a mixed-use building, with 3-parts & 3-stories, it houses overall 419 internal-spaces with 15 catering-spaces & 19 lavatories. These spaces with the activities like cooking, cleaning, drinking, flushing and dripping-water makes up a high annual water-demand profile for the CB. The proposed-research has attempted to indicate the optimal annual water-usae, however, it may vary as per the number of classes and events held (i.e., water-consumption) in the CB in the given year.

5.3. Limitations

5.3.1. Generalizability Limitations

The proposed case-study analyses the conceptual NZE-transformation of only one model-building at Keele University, majorly due to the shorter time-period, allotted to this project. Secondly, the university's large-scale with numerous large, mixed-used buildings is a major limiting-factor for the selection of only single sample-building (i.e., the CB) from entire University. Furthermore, the collection and analysis of a large amount of data for more than one model-building is a challenging-task for research with a pre-decided timeframe. Following to this, the research-process can face technical-constraints like data-mismanagement & knowledge-constraints for imperfect data-analysis. The research-framework for analysing the CB's viability to achieve NZE-status cannot be entirely generalized to other building as each

building indicates a different architectural-orientation, typology and energy-demand. However, the proposed research-framework (**Fig. 26**) can be easily modified and then generalized in the field, depending on the core aims of the project.

Second, the research is restricted to incorporate only a few GBTs (i.e., probability-sampling technique), because assessing the effectiveness and variability of the ‘state-of-the-art’ of all advanced GBTs can become a great challenge for a single researcher in the allotted research-timeframe. The models, orientations and specifications of the retrofitted/installed-GBTs in this case-study cannot be completely generalized to other research, involving the NZEB-development. This is because the building-type, its energy-demand and local-weather conditions may vary for different buildings, locations. However, the mentioned GBTs, in the proposed-research indicate a great range of structural-diversity, suitable for multiple types of buildings.

In the context of generalizability, the case-study research, in general, is often scrutinized. In scientific terms, the case-study research explicitly describes cautions in generalizing the findings of the respective study because of its subjective-nature. However, the common statistical methods, presented in the case-studies are reliable for generalizing and adopting in similar studies to various extent. The quantitative-studies with statistical data-analysis (i.e., here DDA) are often based on probability (i.e., random) sampling, thus, providing the most common-mode of methodological and/or statistical generalization for other studies. However, previous studies have found that even the ideal statistics represents various problems for generalization. This is because the notion of generalization of the scientific-studies are not restricted to statistical-analysis only but extends to interpretation and meaning, more broadly (Lukka and Kasanen, 1995).

5.3.2. Data Collection & Analysis Limitations

The proposed-research involved a few obstacles during the data-collection process, that led the research to certain limitations. For the data-analysis of solar-energy output, generated by the retrofitted/installed solar-GBTs, the PV-tilt angle, azimuth, PR were accurately, yet, directly adopted from existing and/or compiled literature, data-sets and software-tools. Similarly, the data for a few variables like air-density for wind-power output analysis was adopted through reviewing document instead of collecting monthly metred-readings. This is because the proposed-research project is a theoretical-framework for the CB to achieve the NZE-status. Meaning, that no practical retrofits/installations has been checked and/or analysed in the real-world or field. This is a major limiting-factor of the study while analysing the CB’s overall NZE-performance and energy demand-supply profile. However, the variables, mentioned above are considered on the basis of previous-literature in relation to the chosen location for providing a closer insight into the NZE-CBs’ performance-analysis. Despite these limitations, the results, in theory, showed the potential of the CB to harness on-site clean-energy through the GBTs, chiefly because of the building-scale and orientation.

There is a lack of monthly/yearly recorded metred-readings or billing-data of net annual primary water-usage of the CB. This was a limiting-factor in accurately achieving the research’s second-aim i.e., to analyse the CB’s annual water-demand profile. As a result, the priorly compiled/derived-data of water-consumption in large-buildings were directly collected,

modified and adopted through a closer look into the CB's internal-spaces and related activities. Due to this limitation the proposed-study only presents an assumption-based yearly estimations of the CB's water-use.

5.3.3. Methodological Criticism, Scopes & Limitations

The proposed research with a case-study research approach indicates a few methodological limitations, such as subjectivity, that is related specifically to the CB's case. The adopted data-collection & analysis methods to fulfil the objectives and achieve the set aims may slightly vary for different large and/or mixed-use buildings. Quantitative methodological or research-approaches, with positivism, builds on the inductive methods of data-collection & forming the results. Positivism, that is based on factual real-world data cannot fully explain, interpret and/or account for "*how reality is shaped/formed or accepted by the field or people*" in the first place (Blaikie, 2003). Data-collection processes may also become time-consuming, comprehensive & indirect in quantitative research, incorporating various data-collection resources. However, quantitative-research involves randomly selected samples, representing the entire population, therefore, can be generalized (Rahman, 2017) in the field. The random-sampling has not only allowed to consider/adopt the most advanced-GBTs for this case-study but allowed the study to explore & demonstrate the clean energy-generation capacity of the given model-building.

Overall, the quantitative-methodology, used to collect and analyse data in the presented research cannot necessarily be similar for other building-types, geographical-zones, climates. This is because the RETs (i.e., GBTs) are directly linked to the local-weather (Cielo and Subiantoro, 2021). But the undertaken methodological-approach can be adopted, replicated to various extent for analysing the clean-power generation by the retrofitted GBTs, creating green-facades and estimating primary-water usage of the building with the given statistical-methods of DA, scientific-formulas & data-adoption methods.

The scopes of the adopted research methods do not superficially show the direct interlinkage between the Keele university's green-credentials and sustainability-developments in the rural university-settings but demonstrate the actual conceptual-understanding of transforming an existing university-building into an operational-NZEB.

6. Conclusion

This final chapter will conclude the research by briefly summarizing the major findings in relation to the aims and objectives of the proposed research-project. In addition to that, it will review the key research-points & contributions of the research-project along with future recommendations for further research.

With the case study-based research approach, the proposed-research aimed to investigate the viability of the transformation of the CB at Keele University into an operational-NZEB through theoretically retrofitting various GBTs & a passive design feature to generate clean-energy, that equals to the CB's annual energy-demand profile. Second, the research aimed to analyse the estimation-based annual water-demand profile of the CB through reviewing literature. Presently, the CB's annual energy demand is 46,917 kWh (Keele Estate Team). The results of the proposed research indicate that a total of 82 roof/terrace mounted solar-PVs & 8 solar-PV trees generate 29,028 and 16,208 kWh/year of clean-energy, respectively. Next, it shows that total 16 VAWTs generate 3504 kWh/year of clean-energy. Thus, overall, the annual clean energy-generation by the retrofitted and/or installed GBTs is 48,740 kWh (**Table 23**). The results, overall, suggest that the annual clean-energy generation at the CB is more than its annual energy demand. Therefore, based on the analysis of the CB's energy demand & supply profile, it can be concluded that the CB's theoretical or conceptual transformation into a functional NZEB is viable.

Further findings indicate that the assumption-based optimal water-use of the CB is estimated to be 19,170,680.65 litres/year (**Table 25**). The results suggest the CB's high water-consumption, thus, it can be concluded that the CB as a mixed-use building, has a high water-demand profile.

Emerging and distinctly evolving from the sustainable architecture, the concept of net zero energy building established the understanding of balanced energy-metrics in the building-sector. An array of GBTs contribute to the field of NZEBs, among which the solar-PVs and wind-turbines are chief due to the diverse range of cutting-edge innovations and enhanced system-efficiency. However, overall, the field lacks the understanding and measures for the development and wider adaptation of the NZEBs' in non-urban areas. Although, in theory, being a large mixed-use building, this case for the CB provides a conceptual framework for energy-independency measures to adopt a NZE-balance in the rural setting.

Analysing the selected-GBTs' energy output with the standardly pre-derived climate variables indicated the generation of extra-energy after reaching the CB's annual energy demand. This, in theory, suggests that the generated 1823 kWh/year of extra energy can be exported to the main-grid, which constructively support the definition & concept of the NZEBs. Also, in theory, the adaptation of quantitative methodological approaches with exploratory data analysis suggested a good scope for creating a constructive NZEB-framework. Although, the microgeneration through selected helical-VAWTs provide less annual-output than expected, it contributes in achieving the overall energy-balance at the CB. This observation showed that, in practice, the turbines with larger swept-area and efficiency can be integrated in the on-site microgeneration process. The solar-PV tree retrofits of the case-study illustrates the wider practical scopes for adopting novel PV-installations in university-based settings. The observations of conceptually developed green-facades also indicated that the passive designs

can remarkably play role in the building's natural-insulation and cooling, reducing the ambient temperatures, air quality and community well-being.

The CB's theoretically achieved energy-balance suggests the high-scopes of practically achieving the NZE-status as it has suitable spatial, architectural and climatic-conditions. Further research is required in analysing the scopes and limitations of its real-world development. As the CB is one of the largest, mixed-use buildings at Keele, its real-world development will profoundly and positively affect the university's overall energy-outlook. Setting a practical-case, the CB will make a good example of NZEB-development in the UK (Keele University, No Date. a; m). This will further provide a range of R&D scopes to university students, researchers and real-world stakeholders for the development of NZEBs, based in rural, semi-rural and semi-urban location. Furthermore, considering the high-water demand profile of the CB, the real-word development of the project will have high scopes of the involvement of the grey water reuse-systems like the submerged membrane bioreactors. These systems can significantly reduce the primary water-consumption of the CB, however, further research is required to analyse its implementation, capacity and overall performance. NZEBs involve a diverse range of GBTs in the development-process, however, future research is required in the evaluation and selection criteria of the technologies in relation to the model-building, location and its requirement for constructively laying and predicting the expected energy-output.

Overall, the CB at Keele university is theoretically viable to transform into a functional NZEB with the achieved energy-balance, indicating a high scope of its real-world development in the future with the advanced GBTs. Considering the university's overall energy-profile, it can be concluded that the 'net zero energy-CB' will cause significant, constructive changes to the building-performance, energy-outlook & Keele's sustainability profile.

Reference

- Abohela, I., Hamza, N. and Dudek, S., 2013. 'Effect of roof shape, wind direction, building height and urban configuration on the energy yield and positioning of roof mounted wind turbines', *Renewable Energy*, 50, p.1106-1118. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.03.037> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Ade, R. and Rehm, M., 2020. 'The unwritten history of green building rating tools: A personal view from some of the 'founding fathers'', *Building Research & Information*, 48(1), p.1-17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2019.1627179> [Accessed 12 June 2022].
- Almadhhachi, M., Seres, I. and Farkas, I., 2022. 'Significance of solar trees: Configuration, operation, types and technology commercialization', *Energy Reports*, 8, p.6729-6743. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.05.015> [Accessed 23 May 2022].
- Alqurashi, F. and Mohamed, H., 2020. 'Aerodynamic forces affecting the h-rotor darrieus wind turbine', *Modelling and Simulation in Engineering*, 2020. P. 15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1368369> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Amazon, 2022. *12V 24V 48V Wind Helix Spiral Turbine Generator VAWT Vertical Axis Residential Use With PWM MPPT Charger Controller 6000W-White 48v*, Coolwind | amazon.co.uk. [online] Available at: <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Generator-Vertical-Residential-Controller-6000W-White/dp/B08ZSPJRK6?th=1> [Accessed 28 June 2022].
- Awadh, O., 2017. 'Sustainability and green building rating systems: LEED, BREEAM, GSAS and Estidama critical analysis', *Journal of Building Engineering*, 11, p.25-29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2017.03.010> [Accessed 11 June 2022].
- Benjamin, H., 2017. *LEED Link: The LEED project directory*, U.S. Green Building Council. [online] Available at: <https://www.usgbc.org/articles/leed-link-leed-project-directory> [Accessed 13 June 2022].
- Bennetts, H., Radford, A. and Williamson, T., 2002. *Understanding sustainable architecture*. 2nd ed. London: Taylor & Francis, p.176. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203217290> [Accessed 26 April 2022]
- Berndt, E., 2020. 'Sampling methods', *Journal of Human Lactation*, 36(2), p.224-226. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/editorial-board/JHL> [Accessed 3 July 2022].
- Binz, C., Tang, T. and Huenteler, J., 2017. 'Spatial lifecycles of cleantech industries—The global development history of solar photovoltaics', *Energy Policy*, 101, pp.386-402. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.10.034> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Blaikie, N., 2003. *Analyzing Quantitative Data: From Description to Explanation*. 1st ed. London. P.352. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=Tv-YxqWVQ8C&dq=quantitative+data+analysis&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 1 July, 2022]
- Bortolotti, P., Bottasso, C.L., Croce, A. and Sartori, L., 2019. 'Integration of multiple passive load mitigation technologies by automated design optimization—The case study of a medium-size onshore wind turbine', *Wind Energy*, 22(1), p.65-79. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2270> [Accessed 11 July 2022].

- BREEAM, No Date. *How BREEAM Works*, BRE. [online] Available at: <https://bregroup.com/products/breeam/how-breeam-works/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].
- Campbell, T., 2022. *Sustainable Architecture: Ancient Materials & New Practices*, Artland Magazine. [online] Available at: <https://magazine.artland.com/sustainable-architecture-between-ancient-materials-and-new-practices/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].
- Cao, X., Dai, X. and Liu, J., 2016. 'Building energy-consumption status worldwide and the state-of-the-art technologies for zero-energy buildings during the past decade', *Energy and buildings*, 128, pp.198-213. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.06.089> [Accessed 15 June 2022].
- Carter, T., 2016. Discover Le Corbusier's Most Important Architecture, Dezeen. [online] Available at: <https://www.dezeen.com/2016/08/28/world-heritage-le-corbusier-series-modernist-architect-dezeen-pinterest-board/> [Accessed 9 June 2022].
- Castellani, F., Astolfi, D., Peppoloni, M., Natili, F., Buttà, D. and Hirschl, A., 2019. 'Experimental vibration analysis of a small scale vertical wind energy system for residential use', *Machines*, 7(2), p.35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines7020035> [Accessed 27 June 2022].
- Chan, S.H.M., Qiu, L., Esposito, G. and Mai, K.P., 2021. 'Vertical greenery buffers against stress: evidence from psychophysiological responses in virtual reality', *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 213, p.104127. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104127> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Chang, H., Hou, Y., Lee, I., Liu, T. and Acharya, D., 2022. 'Feasibility Study and Passive Design of Nearly Zero Energy Building on Rural Houses in Xi'an, China', *Buildings*, 12(3), p.341. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12030341> [Accessed 6 June 2022].
- Charles, E., 2019. *Best Angle for Solar Panels in the UK and Beyond*, Spirit Solat Ltd. [online] Available at: <https://blog.spiritenergy.co.uk/contractor/best-angle-solar-panels-uk> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Cielo, D. and Subiantoro, A., 2021. 'Net zero energy buildings in New Zealand: Challenges and potentials reviewed against legislative, climatic, technological, and economic factors', *Journal of Building Engineering*, 44, p.102970. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102970> [Accessed 7 May 2022].
- Cole, R., 2020. *Greenery in your home reduces stress, improves health*, Forbes Media LLC. [online] Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/reginacole/2020/11/18/greenery-in-your-home-reduces-stress-improves-health/> [Accessed 11 June 2022].
- Cole, R.J., 2005. 'Building environmental assessment methods: redefining intentions and roles', *Building Research & Information*, 33(5), pp.455-467. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613210500219063> [Accessed 26 April 2022]
- Colquhoun, A., 2002. *Modern architecture*, *Oxford History of Arts*. 1st ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press, p.288. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=uCiQDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=the+oxford+history+of+art+modern+architecture&ots=mgMM8tpED2&sig=1iLAqcW2wP>

[W2RbdO355gdDshqNI&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=the%20oxford%20history%20of%20ar
t%20modern%20architecture&f=false](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.11.014) [Accessed 2 June 2022].

Coma, J., Perez, G., de Gracia, A., Burés, S., Urrestarazu, M. and Cabeza, F., 2017. 'Vertical greenery systems for energy savings in buildings: A comparative study between green walls and green facades', *Building and environment*, 111, p.228-237. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.11.014> [Accessed 7 July, 2022]

Coma, J., Perez, G., de Gracia, A., Burés, S., Urrestarazu, M. and Cabeza, F., 2017. 'Vertical greenery systems for energy savings in buildings: A comparative study between green walls and green facades', *Building and environment*, 111, p.228-237. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.11.014> [Accessed 7 July, 2022]

Conte, E., 2018. 'The era of sustainability: Promises, pitfalls and prospects for sustainable buildings and the built environment', *Sustainability*, 10(6), p.2092. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10062092> [Accessed 15 June 2022].

Conway, H. and Roenisch, R., 2005. *Understanding architecture: an introduction to architecture and architectural history*. Abingdon: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, p.258. Available at: <https://api.taylorfrancis.com/content/books/mono/download?identifierName=doi&identifierValue=10.4324/9780203973196&type=googlepdf> [Accessed 2 May 2022].

Corbusier, L., 2013. *Towards a new architecture*, New York: Courier Corporation, p.320. Available at: https://monoskop.org/images/b/bf/Corbusier_Le_Towards_a_New_Architecture_no_OCR.pdf [Accessed 1 May 2022].

D'Agostino, D. and Mazzarella, L., 2019. 'What is a Nearly zero energy building? Overview, implementation and comparison of definitions', *Journal of Building Engineering*, 21, p.200-212. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2018.10.019> [Accessed 14 June 2022].

Danish, S., Senjyu, T., Ibrahimi, M., Ahmadi, M. and Howlader, M., 2019. 'A managed framework for energy-efficient building', *Journal of Building Engineering*, 21, p.120-128. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2018.10.013> [Accessed 2 May 2022].

Darko, A., Chan, P., Owusu-Manu, G. and Ameyaw, E., 2017. 'Drivers for implementing green building technologies: An International Survey of Experts', *Journal of cleaner production*, 145, p.386-394. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.043> [Accessed 28 May 2022].

de Carniere, L. and Lyng, F., 2016. *Urban Rigger / BIG*, ArchDaily. [online] Available at: <https://www.archdaily.com/796551/urban-rigger-big> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Deng, S., Wang, A. and Dai, J., 2014. 'How to evaluate performance of net zero energy building—A literature research', *Energy*, 71, p.1-16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.05.007> [Accessed 2 May 2022].

DeWitt Wallace Library, 2021. *Research Guide | Types of Research Data*. [online] Available at: <https://libguides.maclester.edu/c.php?g=527786/&p=3608643> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Diwania, S., Agrawal, S., Siddiqui, S. and Singh, S., 2020. 'Photovoltaic–thermal (PV/T) technology: a comprehensive review on applications and its advancement', *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, 11(1), p.33-54. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40095-019-00327-y> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Ebersole, G., 2022. Sustainable Architecture – What is it and Why is it Important ?, Reading Eagle | Media News Group. Available at: <https://www.readingeagle.com/2022/03/08/sustainable-architecture-what-is-it-and-why-is-it-important-column/> [Accessed 6 May 2022].

EIA, 2012. *2012 Commercial Buildings Energy Consumption Survey: Water Consumption in Large Buildings*, U. S. Energy Information Administration. [online] Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/consumption/commercial/reports/2012/water/> [Accessed 9 July 2022].

EIA, 2021. *Net Zero by 2050. A Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector*. Paris: International Energy Agency, p.224. [online] Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/net-zero-by-2050> [Accessed 20 June 2022].

Elprocus, 2022. *What is a Darrius wind turbine and its working*, Electronics | Projects | Focus. [online] Available: <https://www.elprocus.com/darrieus-wind-turbine-working/> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Emes, W., 2021. *Carbon Management Plan. 2016-2022*. Keele: Keele University, p.19. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/media/keeleuniversity/estatesdevelopment/estates/energy/2016-2022%20CMP%20Final.pdf> [Accessed 7 June 2022].

ESCSI, 2022. *LEED Rating System*, ESCSI. [online] Available at: <https://www.escsi.org/sustainability-without-compromise/leed-rating-system/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Eumorfopoulou, A. and Kontoleon, J., 2009. 'Experimental approach to the contribution of plant-covered walls to the thermal behaviour of building envelopes', *Building and Environment*, 44(5), p.1024-1038. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.07.004> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]

Eumorfopoulou, A. and Kontoleon, J., 2009. 'Experimental approach to the contribution of plant-covered walls to the thermal behaviour of building envelopes', *Building and Environment*, 44(5), p.1024-1038. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.07.004> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]

Exploring Solar Panel Efficiency Breakthroughs in 2020, 2020. [Online video] Directed by M. Ferrell. Boston, U.S.A.: Undecided with Matt Ferrell. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2uIOeHCO-r-0> [Accessed 17 June 2022].

Fankhauser, S., Smith, S., Allen, M., Axelsson, K., Hale, T., Hepburn, C., Kendall, J., Khosla, R., Lezaun, J., Mitchell-Larson, E., Obersteiner, M., Rajamani, L., Rickaby, R., Seddon, N. and Wetzer, T., 2021. 'The meaning of net zero and how to get it right', *Nature Climate Change*, 12(1), p.15-21. Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-021-01245-w> [Accessed 4 June 2022].

- Feng, W., Zhang, Q., Ji, H., Wang, R., Zhou, N., Ye, Q., Hao, B., Li, Y., Luo, D. and Lau, S., 2019. 'A review of net zero energy buildings in hot and humid climates: Experience learned from 34 case study buildings', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 114, p.109303. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109303> [Accessed 4 June 2022].
- Gans, D. and Corbusier, L., 2006. *The Le Corbusier Guide*. 3rd ed. New York: Princeton Architectural Press, p.283. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=9bWD3CySg5gC&dq=le+corbusier&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 10 June 2022].
- Gauzin-Müller, D. and Favet, N., 2002. *Sustainable architecture and urbanism*. Basel: Birkhauser, p.255. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Axo0RwWs1TEC&oi=fnd&pg=PA9&dq=what+is+sustainable+architecture&ots=PXq5R3Yap_&sig=8IX8xSbJl8U_qKVS5pCIousB5yY#v=onepage&q=what%20is%20sustainable%20architecture&f=false [Accessed 5 May 2022].
- Geisz, F., France, M., Schulte, L., Steiner, A., Norman, G., Guthrey, L., Young, R., Song, T. and Moriarty, T., 2020. 'Six-junction III–V solar cells with 47.1% conversion efficiency under 143 Suns concentration', *Nature energy*, 5(4), p.326-335. Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41560-020-0598-5> [Accessed 13 June 2022].
- General Electric, 2022. Haliade-X Offshore Wind Turbine, ge.com [online] Available at: <https://www.ge.com/renewableenergy/wind-energy/offshore-wind/haliade-x-offshore-turbine> [Accessed 23 June 2022].
- Gerring, J., 2007. *Case Study Research: Principles and Practices*. 1st ed. Oxford: Cambridge University Press, p.256. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=CbetaQAAQBAJ&dq=case+study+as+quantitative+research&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 30 June, 2022]
- Global Solar Atlas, 2022. PVOUT map | globalsolaratlas.info. [online] Available at: <https://globalsolaratlas.info/> [Accessed 27 June 2022].
- Good, C., Andresen, I. and Hestnes, A.G., 2015. 'Solar energy for net zero energy buildings—A comparison between solar thermal, PV and photovoltaic–thermal (PV/T) systems', *Solar Energy*, 122, p.986-996. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2015.10.013> [Accessed 22 June 2022].
- Google Earth, No Date. a. Keele University 54°37'20.80" N, 2°12'48.25" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].
- Google Earth, No Date. b. Keele University 53°00'13.76" N, 2°13'41.38" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].
- Google Earth, No Date. c. Keele University 53°00'20.16" N, 2°16'45.25" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].
- Google Earth, No Date. d. Chancellor's Building 53°00'14.42" N, 2°16'27.52" W [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Google Earth, No Date. e. Chancellor's Building 53°00'14.84" N, 2°16'26.53" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Google Earth, No Date. f. Chancellor's Building 53°00'13.27" N, 2°16'17.59" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Google Earth, No Date. g. Chancellor's Building 53°00'13.39" N, 2°16'27.54" W. [online] Available at: <https://earth.google.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Goyal, S., Esposito, M. and Kapoor, A., 2018. 'Circular economy business models in developing economies: lessons from India on reduce, recycle, and reuse paradigms', *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 60(5), p.729-740. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/tie.21883> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Grand View Research, 2022. *Building-integrated Photovoltaics Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report by Technology (Crystalline Silicon, Thin Film), By Application, By End-use, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2022 – 2030*. [online] Available at: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/building-integrated-photovoltaics-bipv-market> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Guy, S. and Farmer, G., 2001. 'Reinterpreting Sustainable Architecture: The Place of Technology', *Journal of Architectural Education*, 54(3), p.140-148. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1162/10464880152632451> [Accessed 3 May 2022].

GWA, 2021. Nazka maps | globalwindatlas.com. [online] Available at: <https://globalwindatlas.info/> [Accessed 28 June 2022].

Hox, J. and Boeije, R., 2005. 'Data collection, primary versus secondary', *Encyclopaedia of Social Management*, 1, p. 593-599. Available at: https://dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/23634/hox_05_data+collection.primary+versus+secondary.pdf?sequence= [Accessed 3 July 2022].

Hyams, M.A., 2012. 'Wind energy in the built environment', In *Metropolitan Sustainability*, p. 457-499. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857096463.3.457> [Accessed 26 June 2022].

Hyder, F., Sudhakar, K. and Mamat, R., 2018, Solar PV tree design: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, [online] 82, pp.1079-1096. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.025> [Accessed 23 June 2022].

Ingrams, S., 2022. Solar panel installation, Which? [online] Available at: <https://www.which.co.uk/reviews/solar-panels/article/solar-panels/solar-panel-installation-aiRvu3N6OyEN> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Ionescu, C., Baracu, T., Vlad, G.E., Necula, H. and Badea, A., 2015. 'The historical evolution of the energy efficient buildings', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 49, p.243-253. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.04.062> [Accessed 7 May 2022].

IRENA, 2019. *FUTURE OF WIND*. Deployment, investment, technology, grid integration and socio-economic (A Global Energy Transformation paper). Abu Dhabi: International Renewable Energy Agency, p. 88. [online] Available at: <https://www.irena.org/>

/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2019/Oct/IRENA_Future_of_wind_2019.pdf

[Accessed 26 June 2022].

IRENA, 2021. *Renewable Energy Statistics 2021*. Renewable Energy Highlight. Abu Dhabi: International Renewable Energy Agency, p. 460. [online] Available at: <https://irena.org/publications/2021/Aug/Renewable-energy-statistics-2021> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

IRENA, 2022. *Remap*, Irena.org. [online] Available at: <http://www.irena.org/remap> [Accessed 19 June 2022].

Ishugah, F., Li, Y., Wang, Z. and Kiplagat, K., 2014. 'Advances in wind energy resource exploitation in urban environment: A review', *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 37, p.613-626. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032114003785> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Iype, J., 2019. *BIG builds affordable floating village 'Urban Rigger' in Copenhagen, Denmark*, Design Private Limited. [online] Available at: <https://www.stirworld.com/see-features-big-builds-affordable-floating-village-urban-rigger-in-copenhagen-denmark> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Jacobson, M. and Jadhav, V., 2018. 'World estimates of PV optimal tilt angles and ratios of sunlight incident upon tilted and tracked PV panels relative to horizontal panels', *Solar Energy*, 169, p.55-66. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2018.04.030> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Jaganmohan, M., 2021. *Number of sites generating electricity from solar photovoltaic in the United Kingdom (UK) from 2007 to 2020*, statista.com. [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/418830/number-of-solar-photovoltaic-installations-uk/> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

Jebb, T., Parrigon, S. and Woo, E., 2017. 'Exploratory data analysis as a foundation of inductive research', *Human Resource Management Review*, 27(2), p.265-276. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2016.08.003> [Accessed 30 June 2022].

Johnson, A., 1994. *The Theory of Architecture: Concepts Themes & Practices*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, p.512. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=BJZ8XzXvLvkC&oi=fnd&pg=PR13&dq=the+theory+of+architecture+concepts+themes+and+practices+&ots=PTyyUc_H-B&sig=OSa0rmCmZN46Eibhup1Ipo_IcAk [Accessed 2 May 2022].

Jones, E. and Evans, E., 2016. *Energy Management Strategy. 2016-2022*. Keele: Keele University, p.19. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/media/keeleuniversity/estatesdevelopment/estates/environmental/Energy%20Management%20Strategy%20Final.pdf> [Accessed 9 June 2022].

Jutta, B. and van Zanden, J., 2020. *Primary energy consumption*, Our World in Data. [online] Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/primary-energy-cons?tab=chart> [Accessed 1 June 2022].

Keele University, 2022. *Chancellor's Lecture Theatres*, Keele University - Chancellor's Building. [online] Available at: <https://keele-conference.com/room/lecture-theatres-chancellors-building/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. a. *Energy and carbon*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/about/sustainability/ouoperations/energyandcarbon/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. b. *Keele University Home Page*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. c. *Low carbon energy generation park*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/about/sustainability/ouoperations/energyandcarbon/lowcarbonenergygenerationpark/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. d. *POLKA*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/sustainable-futures/ourchallengethemes/providingcleanenergyreducingcarbonemissions/polka/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. e. *Rugeley*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/sustainable-futures/ourchallengethemes/providingcleanenergyreducingcarbonemissions/rugeley/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. f. *SEND - Smart Energy Network Demonstrator*. [online] Keele University. Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/estates/projects/currentprojects/send-smartenergynetworkdemonstrator/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. g. *SIMULATE*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/sustainable-futures/ourchallengethemes/providingcleanenergyreducingcarbonemissions/simulate/> [Accessed 8 June 2022]

Keele University, No Date. n. *Chancellor's Room Facilities*, Keele University - Chancellor's Building. [online] Available at: <https://keele-conference.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Chancellor%E2%80%99s-Floorplan.pdf> [Accessed 9 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. h. *Chancellor's Central*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/study/campuslife/foodanddrink/restaurantsbarscafesandtakeaways/chancellorscentral/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. i. *Biodiversity*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/about/sustainability/greencampus/biodiversity/#:~:text=We%20have%20a%20varied%20flora,have%20a%20very%20biodiverse%20campus.> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. j. *HyDeploy*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/sustainable-futures/ourchallengethemes/providingcleanenergyreducingcarbonemissions/hydeploy/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. k. *Location*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/business/scienceandinnovationpark/whykeele/location/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. l. *Maps*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/about/howtofindus/maps/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Keele University, No Date. m. *Sustainability*. [online] Available at: <https://www.keele.ac.uk/about/sustainability/> [Accessed 8 June 2022].

Kibert, C., 2016. *Sustainable Construction: Green Building Design and Delivery*. 4th ed. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, p.608. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=2xgWCgAAQBAJ&dq=EMERGENCE+of+green+building&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 1 May 2022].

Kline, B., 2022. *First Along the River: A Brief History of the U.S. Environmental Movement*. 5th ed. Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield, p.288. Available at: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=hGBVEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=industrial+revolution+and+environmental+movement&ots=-17d5w8ljS&sig=d0fICIBU-Vtdn4l4APHe9fhRYes#v=onepage&q=industrial%20revolution%20and%20environmental%20movement&f=false> [Accessed 9 June, 2022]

Knudsen, C., Moreno, E., Arimah, B., Otieno, R. and Ogunsanya, O., 2020. *World Cities Report 2020*. The Value of Sustainable Urbanization. Nairobi: United Nations Human Settlements Programme, p.418. [online] Available at: https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2020/10/wcr_2020_report.pdf [Accessed 5 June 2022].

Koons, E., 2022. *Net-Zero Energy Buildings: A Stepping Stone to Decarbonisation*, Energy Tracker Asia. [online] Available at: <https://energytracker.asia/net-zero-energy-buildings-a-stepping-stone-to-decarbonisation/> [Accessed 5 June 2022].

Kopnina, H., Washington, H., Taylor, B. and J Piccolo, J., 2018. ‘Anthropocentrism: More than just a misunderstood problem’, *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 31(1), p.109-127. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10806-018-9711-1> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Kumar, M., Sudhakar, K. and Samykano, M., 2019. ‘Performance comparison of BAPV and BIPV systems with c-Si, CIS and CdTe photovoltaic technologies under tropical weather conditions’, *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 13, p.100374. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2018.100374> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Kumar, R., Raahemifar, K. and Fung, S., 2018. ‘A critical review of vertical axis wind turbines for urban applications’, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 89, p.281-291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.03.033> [Accessed 2 July 2022].

Laski, J. and Burrows, V., 2022. *FROM THOUSANDS TO BILLIONS*. Coordinated Action towards 100% Net Zero Carbon Buildings By 2050. London: World Green Building Council, p.52. [online] Available at: <http://www.worldgbc.org/news-media/thousands-billions-coordinated-action-towards-100-net-zero-carbon-buildings-2050> [Accessed 5 June 2022].

- Lee, L. and Burnett, J., 2008. 'Benchmarking energy use assessment of HK-BEAM, BREEAM and LEED', *Building and environment*, 43(11), p.1882-1891. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2007.11.007> [Accessed 13 June 2022].
- Lin, B. and Chen, Z., 2022. 'Net zero energy building evaluation, validation and reflection—A successful project application', *Energy and Buildings*, 261, p.111946. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.111946> [Accessed 8 June 2022].
- Liu, Q., Huang, J., Ni, T. and Chen, L., 2022. 'Measurement of China's Building Energy Consumption from the Perspective of a Comprehensive Modified Life Cycle Assessment Statistics Method', *Sustainability*, 14(8), p.4587. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084587> [Accessed 6 May 2022].
- Liu, Z., Zhou, Q., Tian, Z., He, B.J. and Jin, G., 2019. 'A comprehensive analysis on definitions, development, and policies of nearly zero energy buildings in China', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 114, p.109314. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109314> [Accessed 16 June 2022].
- Lobell, J. and Kahn, L., 2008. *Between Silence and Light: Spirit in the Architecture of Louis I. Kahn*. 2nd ed. Shambhala. P.120. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=n5tTPgAACAAJ&printsec=front_cover&redir_esc=y [Accessed 10 June, 2022]
- Lu, Y., Chang, R., Shabunko, V. and Yee, L., 2019. 'The implementation of building-integrated photovoltaics in Singapore: drivers versus barriers. *Energy*', 168, pp.400-408. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.11.099> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Lukka, K. and Kasanen, E., 1995. 'The problem of generalizability: anecdotes and evidence in accounting research', *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 8(5), 7. 71-90. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513579510147733> [Accessed 12 July, 2022]
- Manso, M. and Castro-Gomes, J., 2015. 'Green wall systems: A review of their characteristics', *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 41, p.863-871. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.203> [Accessed 7 July, 2022]
- Manso, M. and Castro-Gomes, J., 2015. 'Green wall systems: A review of their characteristics', *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 41, p.863-871. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.203> [Accessed 7 July, 2022]
- Marszal, J., Heiselberg, P., Bourrelle, S., Musall, E., Voss, K., Sartori, I. and Napolitano, A., 2011. 'Zero Energy Building—A review of definitions and calculation methodologies', *Energy and buildings*, 43(4), p.971-979. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2010.12.022> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Martek, I., Hosseini, R., Shrestha, A., Zavadskas, K. and Seaton, S., 2018. 'The sustainability narrative in contemporary architecture: falling short of building a sustainable future', *Sustainability*, 10(4), p.981. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10040981> [Accessed 8 June 2022].
- Maximize Market Research, 2022. Global Building Applied Photovoltaic (BAPV) Market was valued US\$ XX Bn in 2019 and is expected to reach XX Bn by 2027, at a CAGR of XX %

during a forecast period. [online] Available at: <https://www.maximizemarketresearch.com/market-report/global-catheters-market/32429/> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Mazzeo, D. and Oliveti, G., 2020. 'Advanced innovative solutions for final design in terms of energy sustainability of nearly/net zero energy buildings (nZEB)', *Sustainability*, 12(24), p.10394. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410394> [Accessed 5 June 2022].

McCormick, J., 1991. *Reclaiming Paradise: The Global Environmental Movement*. Indiana University Press, P.259. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=xC16yGp9-HUC&dq=the+history+of+environmental+movement&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 9 June, 2022]

McGinty, D., 2020. *How to Build a Circular Economy*, World Resources Institute. [online] Available at: <https://www.wri.org/insights/how-build-circular-economy> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Met Office, No Date. *UK Climate Averages | Keele*, metoffice.gov.uk. [online] Available at: <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/climate/maps-and-data/uk-climate-averages/gcqmkgel1> [Accessed 26 June 2022].

Miller, N., 2021. *The Industry Creating a Third of the World's Waste | Future Planet Sustainability*, BBC. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20211215-the-buildings-made-from-rubbish> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Morales, A., Martin, M. and Heaney, P., 2009. Methods for Estimating Commercial, Industrial and Institutional Water Use. In: *FSAWWA Water Conference*, Orlando. [online] Available at: <http://www.conservefloridawater.org/publications/10327351.pdf> [Accessed 19 June 2022].

Moreno-Monroy, A., Schiavina, M. and Veneri, P., 2021. 'Metropolitan areas in the world: Delineation and population trends', *Journal of Urban Economics*, 125, p.103242. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2020.103242> [Accessed 28 April 2022].

Ng, K. and Mithraratne, N., 2014. 'Lifetime performance of semi-transparent building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) glazing systems in the tropics', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 31, pp.736-745. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.12.044> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

Nuissl, H. and Siedentop, S., 2021. 'Urbanisation and land use change', *Sustainable Land Management in a European Context*, Springer, Cham, p.75-99. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50841-8_5 [Accessed 7 June 2022].

Nuwer, R., 2012. *The Scientific Reason Complementary Colours Look Good Together*, Smithsonian Magazine. [online] Available at: <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/the-scientific-reason-complementary-colors-look-good-together-114030051/> [Accessed 1 July 2022].

Ochieng, A., 2009. 'An analysis of the strengths and limitation of qualitative and quantitative research paradigms', *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 13, p.13. Available at: https://scientiasocialis.lt/pec/files/pdf/Atieno_Vol.13.pdf [Accessed 2 July 2022].

- OFEE, 2006. *Green Buildings*, Naturalstoneinstitute.org. [online] Available at: <https://www.naturalstoneinstitute.org/default/assets/File/consumers/historystoneingreenbuilding.pdf> [Accessed 24 June 2022].
- Ohene, E., Chan, A. and Darko, A., 2022. 'Review of global research advances towards net-zero emissions buildings', *Energy and Buildings*, 266, p.112142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.112142> [Accessed 6 May 2022].
- Olubunmi, A., Xia, B. and Skitmore, M., 2016. 'Green building incentives: A review', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 59, p.1611-1621. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.028> [Accessed 12 June 2022].
- Omrany, H., Chang, R., Soebarto, V., Zhang, Y., Ghaffarianhoseini, A. and Zuo, J., 2022. 'A Bibliometric Review of Net Zero Energy Building Research 1995–2022', *Energy and Buildings*, p.111996. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.111996> [Accessed 4 June 2022].
- Onion, A., Sullivan, M. and Mullen, M., 2010. *Energy Crisis (1970s)*, HISTORY. [online] Available at: <https://www.history.com/topics/1970s/energy-crisis> [Accessed 11 June 2022].
- Pandey, K., Tyagi, V., Jeyraj, A., Selvaraj, L., Rahim, A. and Tyagi, K., 2016. 'Recent advances in solar photovoltaic systems for emerging trends and advanced applications', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 53, pp.859-884. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.09.043> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Parcell, S., 2012. *Four Historical Definitions of Architecture*. Montréal: McGill-Queen's University Press, p.352. Available at: https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=liL7arj9a24C&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Four+Historical+Definitions+of+Architecture&ots=ZYxLeoAmkz&sig=eySr5Sg63PCdGIggL_nO0EDyYYg [Accessed 1 May 2022].
- Peng, J., Lu, L., Yang, H. and Han, J., 2013. 'Investigation on the annual thermal performance of a photovoltaic wall mounted on a multi-layer façade. *Applied energy*', 112, pp.646-656. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.12.026> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Pérez, G., Coma, J., Martorell, I. and Cabeza, F., 2014. 'Vertical Greenery Systems (VGS) for energy saving in buildings: A review', *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 39, p.139-165. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.055> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]
- Pérez, G., Coma, J., Martorell, I. and Cabeza, F., 2014. 'Vertical Greenery Systems (VGS) for energy saving in buildings: A review', *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 39, p.139-165. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.055> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]
- Perovskite Solar Cells Could be the Future of Energy*, 2021. [Online video] Directed by M. Ferrell. Boston, U.S.A.: Undecided with Matt Ferrell. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YWU89g7sj7s> [Accessed 17 June 2022].
- Photovoltaic Software, 2022. *How to calculate the annual solar energy output of a photovoltaic system?*, photovoltaic-software.com. [online] Available at: <https://photovoltaic->

[software.com/principle-ressources/how-calculate-solar-energy-power-pv-systems](https://www.software.com/principle-ressources/how-calculate-solar-energy-power-pv-systems) [Accessed 26 June 2022].

Plecher, L., 2021. *Development of the world population until 2050*, Statista. Statista.com. [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/262875/development-of-the-world-population/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Polaris Market Research, 2021. *Net-Zero Energy Buildings Market Size, Share & Growth*, Industry Report, 2028. [online] Available at: <https://www.polarismarketresearch.com/industry-analysis/net-zero-energy-buildings-market> [Accessed 14 June 2022].

Qcells, 2021. *Can Windows Be a PV Power Station? Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) is Becoming Popular!* [online] Available at: <https://new-q-cells.com/en/sub.php?idx=818&status=true> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Ragheb, A., El-Shimy, H. and Ragheb, G., 2016. 'Green architecture: A concept of sustainability', *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 216, p.778-787. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.12.075> [Accessed 4 June 2022].

Rahman, M.S., 2017. 'The advantages and disadvantages of using qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods in language "testing and assessment" research: A literature review', *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1), p.12. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/jel.v6n1p102> [Accessed 29 June 2022].

Rashid, Y., Rashid, A., Warraich, A., Sabir, S. and Waseem, A., 2019. 'Case study method: A step-by-step guide for business researchers', *International journal of qualitative methods*, 18, p.1609406919862424. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1609406919862424> [Accessed 30 June 2022].

Ravenscroft, T., 2021. *Pictures of IIMA by Edmund Sumner*, Deezeen. [online] Available at: <https://www.dezeen.com/2021/01/07/louis-kahn-indian-institute-of-management-ahmedabad-dormitories-iima/> [Accessed 9 June 2022].

Reza, A., Tolentino, G. and Toledo, M., 2015. 'Construction of a helical vertical axis wind turbine for electricity supply', *Computer-Aided Design and Applications*, 12(1), p.9-12. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/16864360.2015.1077069> [Accessed 27 June 2022].

RHS, 2022. *Ivy keeps buildings cooler and less damp, research shows*, Royal Horticultural Society, UK. Available at: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/science/articles/ivy-homes> [Accessed 8 July 2022].

Ritchie, H. and Roser, M., 2020. *CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions*, Our World in Data. [online] Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-emissions> [Accessed May 27, 2022].

Ritchie, H. and Roser, M., 2022. *Solar PV Cumulative Capacity*, Our World in Data. [online] Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/solar-pv-cumulative-capacity> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

- Ritchie, H. and Roser, M., 2022. *Urbanization*, Our World in Data. [online] Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/urbanization#:~:text=Urbanization%20is%20a%20trend%20unique,areas%20as%20they%20become%20richer>. [Accessed 1 June 2022].
- Ritchie, H., Roser, M. and Rosado, P., 2022. *Energy*, Our World in Data. [online] Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/energy-production-consumption> [Accessed April 28 2022].
- Robinson, Z. and Briggs, S., 2018. *Keele Sustainability Report*. 2018. Keele: Keele University, p.48. [online] Available at: <http://file:///C:/Users/welcome/Downloads/KEELE%20Sustainability%20Report%20v2.pdf> [Accessed 12 July 2022].
- Roe, J.J., Thompson, C.W., Aspinall, P.A., Brewer, M.J., Duff, E.I., Miller, D., Mitchell, R. and Clow, A., 2013. 'Green space and stress: evidence from cortisol measures in deprived urban communities', *international journal of environmental research and public health*, 10(9), p.4086-4103. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/10/9/4086> [Accessed 13 July 2022].
- Roth, L. and Clark, A., 2019. *Understanding architecture: Its Elements, History, and Meaning*. 3rd ed. New York: Routledge, p.816. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429495588> [Accessed 1 May 2022].
- RTS, No Date. *What is LEED Certification & Steps for Getting a Certification*, Recycle Track Systems. [online] Available at: <https://www.rts.com/resources/guides/what-is-leed-certification/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].
- Safikhani, T., Abdullah, M., Ossen, R. and Baharvand, M., 2014. 'A review of energy characteristic of vertical greenery systems', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 40, p.450-462. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.166> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]
- Safikhani, T., Abdullah, M., Ossen, R. and Baharvand, M., 2014. 'A review of energy characteristic of vertical greenery systems', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 40, p.450-462. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.07.166> [Accessed 6 July, 2022]
- Saini, L., Meena, S., Raj, P., Agarwal, N. and Kumar, A., 2022. 'Net Zero Energy Consumption building in India: An overview and initiative toward sustainable future', *International Journal of Green Energy*, 19(5), pp.544-561. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15435075.2021.1948417> [Accessed 15 June 2022].
- Sartori, I., Napolitano, A. and Voss, K., 2012. 'Net zero energy buildings: A consistent definition framework', *Energy and buildings*, 48, p.220-232. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.01.032> [Accessed 2 May 2022].
- Schupak, A., 2021. *Circular Economy: Wind Turbine Blade Maker Is Working to Turn Waste into a Resource*, ge.com [online] Available at: <https://www.ge.com/news/reports/circular-economy-wind-turbine-blade-maker-is-working-to-turn-waste-into-a-resource> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Schwarzenegger, A., 2014. *Smartflower POP – the world's first all-in-one solar system*. SIMPLY SET-UP, CONNECT AND PRODUCE CLEAN ELECTRICITY. Gussing: SmartFlower, p. 24. [online] Available at: <http://smartboxpanama.com/data/documents/Smart-Flower-Brochure.pdf> [Accessed 24 June 2022].

Sena, S., 2021. *Calculating Optimal Azimuth Angle for Solar Panels*, solarsena.com. [online] Available at: <https://solarsena.com/calculating-optimal-azimuth-angle-solar-panels/> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Shan, M. and Hwang, G., 2018. 'Green building rating systems: Global reviews of practices and research efforts', *Sustainable cities and society*, 39, p.172-180. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.02.034> [Accessed 13 June 2022].

Shirinbakhsh, M. and Harvey, D., 2021. 'Net-zero energy buildings: The influence of definition on greenhouse gas emissions', *Energy and Buildings*, 247, p.111118. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111118> [Accessed 4 June 2022].

Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy, 2021. *Siemens Gamesa pioneers wind circularity: launch of world's first recyclable wind turbine blade for commercial use offshore* [online] Available at: <https://www.siemensgamesa.com/en-int/newsroom/2021/09/launch-world-first-recyclable-wind-turbine-blade> [Accessed 25 June 2022].

Solar Trees, No Date. *Solar-Powered Tree | Lift from Spotlight Solar — Solar Trees | Spotlight Solar*, spotlight solar.com. [online] Available at: <https://spotlightsolar.com/solar-powered-tree-lift> [Accessed 27 June 2022].

Spotlight Solar, No Date, *Solar-Powered Tree | Lift from Spotlight Solar — Solar Trees*, spotlight solar.com. [online] Available at: <https://spotlightsolar.com/solar-powered-tree-lift> [Accessed 22 June 2022].

Steenberg, C., 2021. *Why Performance Ratio Metrics Are a Thing of the Past*, PVtech. [online] Available at: <https://www.pv-tech.org/why-performance-ratio-metrics-are-a-thing-of-the-past/> [Accessed 26 June 2022].

SunPower, No Date. *475-450W Commercial M-Series Panel*. <https://us.sunpower.com/sites/default/files/m-series-475-460-450-com-datasheet-539976-reva.pdf> [Accessed June 28, 2022].

Tavner, P., Edwards, C., Brinkman, A. and Spinato, F., 2006. 'Influence of wind speed on wind turbine reliability', *Wind Engineering*, 30(1), p.55-72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1260/02F030952406777641441> [Accessed 7 July 2022].

The School of Life, 2022. *Louis Kahn - The School of Life*. [online] Available at: <https://www.theschooloflife.com/article/the-great-architects-louis-kahn/> [Accessed 10 June 2022].

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 2021. *2021 GLOBAL STATUS REPORT FOR BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTION*. Towards a zero-emissions, efficient and resilient buildings and construction sector. Nairobi: The United Nations, p.105. [online] Available at: https://globalabc.org/sites/default/files/2021-10/GABC_Buildings-GSR-2021_BOOK.pdf [Accessed 3 June 2022].

Thompson, B., 2009. 'Descriptive data analysis', *Air medical journal*, 28(2), p.56-59. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amj.2008.12.001> [Accessed 2 July 2022].

Torcellini, P., Pless, S., Deru, M. and Crawley, D., 2006. Zero Energy Buildings: A Critical Look at the Definition. In: *Study National Renewable Energy Lab. (NREL), Golden, CO*

(United States), California: The US Department of Energy. [online] Available at: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/883663> [Accessed 19 June 2022].

Turgeon, A. and Morse, E., 2022. *Wind | Wind is the movement of air caused by the uneven heating of the Earth by the sun*, National Geographic Society. [online] Available at: <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/wind> [Accessed 26 June 2022].

UKGBC, 2022. *NZEB Roadmap*, Nzebnew.pivotaldesign.biz. [online] Available at: <https://www.ukgbc.org/ukgbc-work/net-zero-whole-life-roadmap-for-the-built-environment/> [Accessed 17 June 2022].

United Nations, No Date. *Sustainability*, United Nations. [online] Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/sustainability#:~:text=In%201987%2C%20the%20United%20Nations,development%20needs%2C%20but%20with%20the> [Accessed 2 June 2022].

Urban Rigger, 2020. *Home - Urban Rigger*. [online] Available at: <https://www.urbanrigger.com/> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Ürge-Vorsatz, D., Khosla, R., Bernhardt, R., Chan, Y.C., Vérez, D., Hu, S. and Cabeza, L.F., 2020. 'Advances toward a net-zero global building sector', *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 45, p.227-269. Available at: <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/abs/10.1146/annurev-environ-012420-045843> [Accessed 20 June 2022].

USGBC, 2022. *Mission and vision*, U.S. Green Building Council. [online] Available at: <https://www.usgbc.org/about/mission-vision> [Accessed 12 June 2022].

Vasel, A. and Iakovidis, F., 2017. 'The effect of wind direction on the performance of solar PV plants', *Energy Conversion and Management*, 153, p.455-461. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.09.077> [Accessed 27 June 2022].

Videos

Von Frantzius, I., 2004. 'World Summit on Sustainable Development Johannesburg 2002: A critical analysis and assessment of the outcome', *Environmental Politics*, 13(2), p.467-473. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644010410001689214> [Accessed 15 June 2022].

Wells, L., Rismanchi, B. and Aye, L., 2018. 'A review of Net Zero Energy Buildings with reflections on the Australian context', *Energy and Buildings*, 158, p.616-628. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.10.055> [Accessed 7 June 2022].

Wells, L., Rismanchi, B. and Aye, L., 2018. 'A review of Net Zero Energy Buildings with reflections on the Australian context', *Energy and Buildings*, 158, pp.616-628. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.10.055> [Accessed 7 June 2022].

Why We Should be Putting Solar Panel on Our Fields and Lakes, 2022. [Online video] Directed by Monika Sax. Germany: DW Planet A. Available at: <https://youtu.be/2hwpXCjmkRo> [Accessed 23 June 2022].

Wilberforce, T., Olabi, G., Sayed, T., Elsaid, K., Maghrabie, M. and Abdelkareem, A., 2021. 'A review on zero energy buildings—Pros and cons', *Energy and Built Environment*, p. 14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbenv.2021.06.002> [Accessed 4 June 2022].

- Wills, B., 2014. *The Advantages and Limitations of Single Case Study Analysis*, E-International Relations | Rootsy. Available at: <https://www.e-ir.info/2014/07/05/the-advantages-and-limitations-of-single-case-study-analysis/> [Accessed 30 June 2022].
- Wines, J., 2019. Green Architecture, *Encyclopedia Britannica*. [online] Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/art/green-architecture>. [Accessed 11 June 2022].
- Wong, H., Tan, K., Tan, Y., Sia, A. and Wong, C., 2010. 'Perception studies of vertical greenery systems in Singapore', *Journal of Urban Planning and Development*, 136(4), p.330-338. Available at: <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/%28ASCE%29UP.1943-5444.0000034> [Accessed 5 July, 2022]
- Wong, H., Tan, K., Tan, Y., Sia, A. and Wong, C., 2010. 'Perception studies of vertical greenery systems in Singapore', *Journal of Urban Planning and Development*, 136(4), p.330-338. Available at: <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/%28ASCE%29UP.1943-5444.0000034> [Accessed 5 July, 2022]
- World Green Building Council (WGBC), 2022. *Home*, World Green Building Council. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldgbc.org/> [Accessed 14 June 2022].
- Wu, W. and Skye, M., 2021. 'Residential net-zero energy buildings: Review and perspective', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 142, p.110859. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110859> [Accessed 17 June 2022].
- Yudelson, J., 2010. *The green building revolution.*, Washington: Sland Press., p. 272. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=4s8OMWoO00QC&dq=green+building+rating+tools+jerry+yudelson&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s [Accessed 14 June 2022].
- Zhao, Z., Wang, D., Wang, T., Shen, W., Liu, H. and Chen, M., 2022. 'A review: Approaches for aerodynamic performance improvement of lift-type vertical axis wind turbine', *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 49, p.101789. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101789> [Accessed 25 June 2022].
- Zilberman, M., 2017. 'Optimization of Small, Low Cost, Vertical Axis Wind Turbine for Private and Institutional Use', *Research Gate*, P. 9. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15724.67202> [Accessed 27 June 2022].
- Zion Market Research, 2022. *Vertical Axis Wind Turbines Market-Global Industry Analysis*, zionmarketresearch.com. [online] Available at: <https://www.zionmarketresearch.com/report/vertical-axis-wind-turbine-market> [Accessed 23 June 2022].

Appendices

[A] Data-Tables

1. A Table Showing Global Population (Billion), Global Urban Population (Billion) & Annual CO2 Emissions (Billion Tonnes) from 1965 to 2020

Year	Global Population (Billion) (Redrawn after Ritchie and Roser, 2020; Roser et al., 2020)	Global Urban Population (Billion) (Redrawn after Ritchie and Roser et al., 2020)	Global Primary Energy Consumption (TWh) (Jutta and van Zanden, 2020; Ritchie et al., 2020)	Annual CO2 Emissions (Fossil Fuel and Land Use Change) (Billion Tonnes) (Ritchie and Roser, 2020)
1965	3.34	2.14	43,116	16.51
1970	3.7	2.34	56,722	19.61
1975	4.08	2.53	66,553	22.24
1980	4.46	2.69	77,612	23.64
1985	4.87	2.84	83,896	25.22
1990	5.33	3.01	95,039	26.76
1995	5.74	3.15	1,00,524	28.22
2000	6.14	3.26	1,09,575	29.77
2005	6.54	3.31	1,26,840	33.07
2010	6.96	3.57	1,40,383	37.62
2015	7.38	3.96	1,51,226	40.26
2020	7.79	4.36	1,54,620	38.02

2. A Table Drawing the Research-Boundaries and Related Milestones for Each Step of the Proposed Research (See, **Fig 26**)

Stage	Milestone (M)	Task Remark
I: Research Exploration	1	-Establishing Aims, Objectives and Major Research Approach
II: Data Exploration & Data Collection	2,3,4	-Primary and Secondary Data Collection by Existing Data and Compiled or Derived Data-Collection Methods (Major Methodological Steps)
III: Data Analysis	5	-Analysing Collected Data by Exploratory Data Analysis Approach (Major Methodological Steps)
IV: Achievement of Both Aims by Major Findings	6	-Establishing Major Findings of the Proposed Study
V: Discussion	7	-Analysing & Interpreting Major Results and Analysing Research Limitations

VI: Conclusion	8	-Concluding the Final Viewpoints and Making Future Recommendations
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3. Architectural Specifications of Urban-Rigger Project, Copenhagen, Denmark (Urban Rigger, 2020)

Project Details	
Location of the Project	Copenhagen
Area Covered	680 square metres
Year of the Project Completion	2019
Architect Group	Bjarke Ingels
Floor Levels	2
Hull Block Weight	520 Tons
One Urban-Rigger Loop	12 Apartments (6 on each floor) with communal spaces
Thickness of the Side Wall	20 cm
Side Wall Dimensions	7.4 m to 10.8 m
Thickness of the Bottom Deck	25 cm
Monthly Rent per Apartment	7250 Danish Kroners depending upon the location and apartment orientation
Apartment Area-Cover	30 metre square (Double Bedrooms En-Suite)
Apartment Area-Cover	23 metre square (Double Single-Room En-Suite)
Installed GBTs	
Hydro Heat Pump with Floor Heating System	17 kW
Hanwha Q-Cells Solar PV	7.5 kW

4. Alignment of the Project Urban Rigger with the Following UNSDGs (The United Nations, No Date)

UNSDG No.	Goal	Remark
Goal 7	Affordable & Clean Energy	Urban Rigger comprises solar PVs, Hydro-Heat Pumps and Floor Heating Systems for house-heating and electricity.
Goal 9	Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure	The project design is sustainable and easily replicable, that has incorporated a range of local and international stakeholders like business partners, engineering groups, architects and urban planners and researchers.
Goal 10	Reduced Inequality	An energy efficient, affordable and healthy housing schemes for students.
Goal 11	Sustainable Cities & Communities	Copenhagen's boundaries are expanding due to the urbanization and land-use changes, thus, to cope with anthropogenic issues, schemes like Urban-Rigger is not just smart but also efficient

		and sustainable fostering healthy communal and urban living.
Goal 12	Responsible Consumption & Production	The project materials are used, recycled and environmentally sustainable with no to minimum eco-impacts to its surrounding with low carbon-footprints.

5. A Table Showing Specifications of Different NZ-building Terms

Term	Explanation of the Term
Site NZEB (Shirinbakhsh and Harvey, 2021)	<i>“The energy generation within the building is equal to the building’s total energy use.”</i>
Source NZEB (Shirinbakhsh and Harvey, 2021)	<i>“Generates as much as primary-energy as it uses within the site.”</i>
Nearly Net Zero Energy Building (Shirinbakhsh and Harvey, 2021)	<i>“A building with a high energy-performance that very low amount of energy is covered by the on-site or nearby clean-energy resources.”</i>
Net Zero Carbon Building (WGBC, 2022; D'Agostino and Mazzarella, 2019)	<i>“These are very highly efficient net zero buildings with on and/or off-site clean energy resources and here, no carbon is given off, meaning, it is 100% self-reliant and energy efficient with fully achieved carbon neutrality.”</i> However, there is a lack of a clear, universally accepted definition.

6. Terminology of the NZEBs (Sartori et al., 2012; Wu and Skye, 2021)

Term	Explanation
Energy-Grid	<i>“An energy-supply system from producers and suppliers to consumers.”</i>
Delivered Energy	<i>“This is the specific amount of energy, that flows from grid to the building-structures in certain time-period or it is simply called the imported-energy.”</i>
Exported Energy	<i>“Opposite to delivered -energy, in direction, this energy flows from the buildings, specified per energy-carriers in kWh/year or certain time-period.”</i>
Generation	<i>“The total energy-production of the building, specified per energy-carriers in kWh/year or certain time-period.”</i>
Load	<i>“Load is the structures’ energy-demand, specified per energy-carriers in kWh/year or certain time-period.”</i>
Weighting-System	<i>“It is also called ‘metrics-system’ as it converts the physical-units into other metrics, such as the emissions generated by the energy-extraction, energy-generation and energy-delivery process.”</i>
Net Zero Energy Balance	<i>“NZE-balance is a measure or condition, when the overall exported-energy or weighted-supply meets or exceeds the overall delivered-energy or weighted-demand.”</i>

	In other words, NZE balance means: Weighted-Supply - Weighted Demand = 0 (Sartori et al., 2012)
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7. A Table Showing the Global Solar PV Cumulative Capacity in Megawatt from 1996 to 2021 (Ritchie and Roser, 2022)

Year	Global Solar PV Cumulative Capacity in Megawatt
1996	171.81
2000	808.67
2005	4548.12
2010	40,337.81
2015	223,203.59
2021	843,086.06

8. A Table Showing a Drop in the Global Average Prices in US\$ per Watt of Solar PV Modules from 1976 to 2019 (Ritchie and Roser, 2022)

Year	Prices in US \$/Watt
1976	106.09
1980	35.01
1985	14.85
1990	8.81
1995	5.83
2000	4.88
2005	4.24
2010	2.04
2015	0.60
2019-20	0.38

9. Type of Presently Existing Solar-Cell Technologies (Diwania et al., 2020; Ferrell, 2020; Geisz et al., 2020)

Type of Solar PV Cell	Efficiency	Remark
Monocrystalline c-Si	-Highly efficient with around 15-23% of efficiency and 25-30 years of overall lifespan -Thickness can be around 200 µm	-A Wafer Type/Shaped PV-structures, made from Silicon -High Cost -Current Market Value: \$4.1 billion - 2029 Market Value: \$7.11 billion
Poly-Crystalline c-Si	-Good efficiency with around 12-18% with an average 27 years of lifespan -Thickness can be around 200 µm	- A Wafer Type/Shaped PV-structures, made from Silicon -Less efficient than the Monocrystalline c-Si but are cost-efficient & are easy to manufacture
Thin-Film (TF)	-Least Efficient type with around 8 to 14% of	-Thin layers of semiconducting

	efficiency and less than 20 years of lifespan -Thinner than the Silicon-based PVs, in nanometres	materials and are cost-efficient -The next-generation technologies - The CAGR of the TF market from 2020-2025 is predicted to reach around 20.02%
Amorphous Silicon (a-Si)	-A non-crystalline, low-efficiency (~15%), TF-type of silicon based photovoltaic with a Wafer like Structures	-Very small share in the global PV market , but is preferred in the TF market over its counterparts
Cadmium Telluride (CdTe)	-Low efficiency with higher payback period -Efficiency can reach up to 17-18%	-The most common TF type of solar-PV, occupying 50% of the TF market, globally -Under scrutiny, because of the harmful impacts of materials like Cd on environment and resources
Copper Indium Selenide (CIS)	-A TF technology with an average efficiency of 15-20%.	-Very small share in the PV market
6-Layered Cells	Around 47.1% of solar-conversion efficiency	Made with alloys of III-V semiconductors (i.e., Aluminium, Phosphorous, Gallium, Arsenic, Indium, Antimony)

10. A Table of Secondary Data: Total Number of Internal-Spaces or Building Rooms & Annual Energy-Consumption Profile of the Chancellor’s Building, Keele University, UK (Data received from the Keele Estate Team)

Total Area Cover	Area in m ²
Total Area (Ground-Cover of the Building; Roof Data Unavailable)	8786.7 m ²
Assumption-Based Total Roof Cover	~170 m ²
Note: total roof-area cover data, not available	
Type of the Spaces/Building Rooms	Total Number of Spaces/Rooms
Teaching Rooms, Research Staff Rooms	224
Research Rooms	3
Teaching Spaces	44
Teaching Staff Support Spaces (Including the Copy, Kitchen and Store Rooms)	50

Teaching Staff Support Spaces (Including the Copy, Kitchen, Store, All Meeting Rooms)	35
Support Staff Offices	29
Catering Spaces (Including the Central Café-Space and Kitchens)	15
Lavatories	19
Total Spaces	419
Locations & Annual Energy Use (kWh)	
Keele University	74,30,106
The Chancellor's Building	46,917
Note: Annual water usage Data of the CB is unavailable.	

11. A Table Showing the Specifications of the Selected, Rooftop Solar-PVs Retrofit (SunPower, No Date)

PV-Type: SunPower Maxeon Commercial M-Series Solar PVs	
Power (P)	475 watt or 0.475 kw
Panel Efficiency (%)	22.3%
Operating Conditions: Temperature (°C)	-40 TO +85 °C
Weigh (kg)	22.7 kg
Size of One Panel in the Leaf	Length: 2047 mm & Width: 1039 mm (or 2.047m & 1.039m, respectively)
Size of the Leaf	Length:3.117m & Width:4.08 m
Test Load (Maximum)	Snow: 187 psf, 9000 Pa, 917 kg/m ³ Front & Wind: 125 psf, 6000 Pa, 611 kg/m ³ Back
Appearance	Class-A with 72 Maxeon 6 Cells & with High-Transmission Tempered Anti-Reflective Glass
Cell Type	Maxeon Gen 6 COM
Junction Box	IP-68 PV4S
Warranty Period	25 Years

12. A Table Showing an Average Yearly Data from the Year 1990 to 2020, Keele, UK (Met Office, No Date)

Location: 52.99, -2.27, Keele, Staffordshire, UK					
Altitude: 178m above Mean Sea-Level					
Data by Keele Observation Station					
Month	Average or Mean Temperature (°C)	Sunshine Hours	Rainfall (mm)	Monthly Mean Wind Speed at 10m (knots)	Monthly Average for Newcastle under Lyme, 2022 (kph)
January	3.93	53.62	67.72	9.48	20.7
February	4.27	75.08	56.77	9.01	20.0
March	6.1	113.13	53.66	9.37	19.2
April	6.44	155.07	53.79	8.44	17.1

May	11.3	190.52	63.21	8.16	16.5
June	13.98	169.95	70.60	6.83	15.5
July	16	182.81	69.60	7.32	15.3
August	15.79	168.12	78.99	7.01	15.4
September	13.49	129.37	72.08	7.15	16.6
October	10.18	100.21	82.71	8.10	18.0
November	6.65	59.18	76.69	8.40	18.6
December	4.23	50.81	82.10	8.55	19.5
Annual Average or Mean (M)	9.6	1447.87	8277.92	8.15	17.7

13. A Table Showing Solar Tree System Specifications (Edited after Solar Trees, No Date; SunPower, No Date)

Lift-Type Solar PV Tree System	
Solar PV Leaves:	PV-Type: SunPower Maxeon Commercial M-Series Solar PVs (6 Solar PV in Single Leaf)
No. of Solar PV Leaf	2 (Total 12 Solar Modules PV Modules)
Single Leaf Size	Length: 4.08m & Width: 3.12m
Total Solar PV Leaf Size in m ²	12.7 m ²
Solar-Tree efficiency	22.3%
Stem Height	6.87 m
Wind Rating	175 MPH
Tree Shade Area on the Ground	Around 250 sq. ft.
Design Features	2 Branched Stem of 80% Recycled Steel with an LED Light Rim around the PV-Leaves

14. A Table Showing the Specifications of the Retrofitted VAWTs for the Proposed Case-Study (Edited after Amazon, 2022)

Model Type	Helix or Helical Spiral Type VAWT
Number of Turbine Blades	2
Basal-Mounting Shaft	1
System Control	Electromagnetic
Generator	3-Phase Permanent Magnet Suspension Motor with 90% efficiency
System	S-V-6000W Helix or Helical Spiral Type VAWT
Turbine Blade-Material	Basalt
Maximum Power in Watts	6500 W
Maximum Speed (m/s)	No More Than 45 m/s
Noise	Minimal
Wight of the System (in kg)	10 kg to ~12 kg
Operational Wind Speed (m/s)	2 m/s
Operation Climate (°C)	-25°C to about +45°C
Diameter (D) (in m)	0.525 m

Height of the Turbine Blade (in m)	1.05 m
Turbine Efficiency (n_T) (in %)	30% or 0.3
Generator Efficiency (n_G) (in %)	90% or 0.9
Voltage Designation (in Volt)	48 V
Mounting Height (in m)	~ 7.5 to 8 m

[B] Visual Representation: Graphs

1. A Graph Indicating the Rising Trends of Global Urbanization, Including Global Rural and Urban Population from 1960 to 2020 (Redrawn after Ritchie and Roser, 2018)

2. Global Renewable Energy Generation by Renewable-Resource from 1965 to 2021 (Ritchie et al., 2022) (For the Live Version of the Graph, Visit: <https://ourworldindata.org/energy-production-consumption>)

[C] Visual Representation: Images & Maps

1. A Digital Campus-Map of Keele University (Keele University, No Date. l)

2. The Chancellor's Building, Facing South to South-East Direction at Keele University, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00'14.84" N and Longitude 2°16'26.53" W (Google Earth, No Date. e)

3. The Chancellor's Building, Keele University, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00'13.27" N and Longitude 2°16'17.59" W (Google Earth, No Date. f)

4. The Chancellor's Building, Keele University, Image Coordinates: Latitude 53°00'13.39" N and Longitude 2°16'27.54" W (Google Earth, No Date. g)

5. A Digital Floor Map of the Chancellor's Building, Keele University: Ground Floor, CBA (Data Received from the Keele Estate Team)

7. A Digital Floor Map of the Chancellor's Building, Keele University: First Floor, CBA
 (Data Received from the Keele Estate Team)

8. The Chancellor's Building Room Facilities Plan: Model Building CBA (Keele University, No Date n.)

9. Solar-PV Orientation Tilt angles and Optimal Output Range (Charles, 2019)

ORIENTATION	WEST					SOUTH					EAST				
Tilt	90°	70°	50°	40°	30°	20°	10°	0°	-10°	-20°	-30°	-40°	-50°	-70°	-90°
0°	87%	90%	92%	92%	93%	93%	93%	93%	93%	93%	92%	92%	91%	89%	86%
10°	84%	90%	94%	95%	95%	96%	96%	97%	97%	96%	95%	94%	93%	89%	84%
20°	82%	90%	94%	96%	97%	98%	99%	99%	98%	97%	96%	95%	93%	88%	81%
30°	78%	87%	93%	96%	97%	98%	99%	100%	98%	97%	96%	95%	93%	85%	78%
40°	75%	84%	92%	94%	95%	96%	96%	96%	96%	95%	94%	92%	90%	82%	72%
50°	70%	79%	87%	90%	91%	93%	94%	94%	94%	93%	91%	88%	83%	76%	70%
60°	65%	73%	80%	83%	86%	87%	87%	87%	88%	87%	85%	82%	78%	71%	63%
80°	50%	60%	66%	68%	69%	70%	71%	72%	72%	71%	70%	67%	66%	57%	50%